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Assignment 1: Evaluation

Exercise 1: Create multi-reference datasets (online)

My target language is Thai. The content of the text is quite challenging because it contains many proper names and technical terms in the economic field.

Exercise 2: Manual and automatic evaluation (Puhti)

[1] The annotated rankings and output scripts can be found at
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/19m8C6or2Yo8Gwq5g8MtYdy7FBuU4WZrjJSnmnrKS4/edit?usp=sharing>

Average Ranks, BLEU, and chrF2

The results from averageRanking.py, BLEU, and chrF2 scores are as follow:

	[2] Average Rank*	Average BLEU Score	Average chrF2 Score
System 1	2.30	11.4	41.5
System 2	2.10	5.7	35.8
System 3	2.60	20.0	50.3
System 4	3.00	15.5	42.9

*The closer to 1, the better.

[3] Assuming that the highest Average rank corresponds to the neural MT system, which is the most favored, followed by the statistical MT system and the rule-based MT system as the least favored, I can make educated guesses. System 2, with an average rank of 2.10, stands out as the top-performing system, likely representing a neural machine translation system known for its high translation quality. System 1 closely follows with an average rank of 2.30, likely indicating a statistical machine translation system, which, despite being older, can still deliver competitive results in specific cases. System 3, with an average rank of 2.60, falls in the middle, possibly representing another neural machine translation system that performed well but not exceptionally. Lastly, System 4, with the lowest average ranking of 3.00, may be a rule-based machine translation system, which often has limitations in handling complex language structures but can still provide adequate performance. This ranking order suggests a preference for neural MT systems, followed by statistical systems, with rule-based systems ranking lower, aligning with common expectations in machine translation evaluation.

[3] When considering BLEU and chrF2 scores together with the rankings, it is interesting to note that System 3 seems to come first. The highest chrF2 score for System 3 (50.3) supports this ranking. The BLEU score for System 3 (20.0) also aligns with the high ranking but is not as strong as the chrF2 score. Although System 4 is ranked lowest, its chrF2 score (42.9) is better than the scores of System 1 and System 2 but still below that of System 3. The BLEU score for System 4 (15.5) is in the middle, indicating that it doesn't strongly correlate with the rankings. Systems 1 and 2 have average performance in between Systems 3 and 4 given all rankings and scores. Their BLEU and chrF2 scores reflect this. Although System 2 has the highest average ranking (2.10), its BLEU and chrF2 scores are second to the lowest (5.7 and 35.8 respectively). System 3 with the average ranking in the middle, on the other hand, has the highest BLEU and chrF2 score, while System 4 has the lowest average that matches its lower ranking.

[3] Evaluation with a Lowercase

	Average BLEU Score (lowercase)	Average chrF2 Score (lowercase)
System 1	12.1	42.6
System 2	5.8	36.3
System 3	20.6	50.9
System 4	16.9	43.8

Converting both reference and candidate texts to lowercase has generally led to improved BLEU and chrF2 scores for all systems proportionally when compared to the original texts with a mixed case, so it does not affect the rankings (3>4>1>2). The scores are demonstrated above. This improvement suggests that the use of lowercase text in the evaluation process has resulted in more favorable translation quality assessments. However, the degree of improvement varies for each system, with some experiencing more significant enhancements than others.

Exercise 3

Domain effects in online MT systems: ChatGPT(3.5), Yandex, and Google Translate

The original text in Thai with English translations can be found at <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1n-Vby64R6shloVHz8vwPPFIq-MLhEsVCBi1egevu62s/edit?usp=sharing>.

After a quick review of the translations produced by the three programs, my initial impression is that ChatGPT exhibits the fewest errors. These errors consist of two Thai proper names and one abbreviation, which are highlighted with red and blue underlines in the Google Docs. These are the only errors present in the output from ChatGPT. Conversely, Yandex and Google Translate both exhibit errors primarily related to the spelling of Thai proper names, with 19 and 6 errors, respectively. Yandex also has four errors in the capitalization of the first letter of sentences, while Google Translate does not have such capitalization issues. Additionally, Google Translate has five punctuation errors, often omitting full stops to separate sentences, and two grammatical errors stemming from the omission of a subject, which is a common characteristic of the Thai language. In terms of fluency, it can be concluded that ChatGPT performs the best, followed by Yandex and Google Translate.

As for the criterion of adequacy, it is evident from the examples provided below that ChatGPT frequently omits significant portions of the source text, particularly proper names, such as "Royal Rainmaking operations" (ปฏิบัติการฝนหลวง) and "Deputy Prime Minister Somsak" (รองนายกฯ สมศักดิ์), which may be considered a severe mistake in translation tasks.

Original text	ปฏิบัติการเติมน้ำอย่างมีประสิทธิภาพ ทั้ง <u>ปฏิบัติการฝนหลวง</u> เติมน้ำใต้ดิน และสูบน้ำในพื้นที่มีศักยภาพ
ChatGPT	Implementing efficient water storage, groundwater recharge, and water pumping in areas with potential.
Yandex	Efficient water replenishment operation, including <u>Royal rain</u> , groundwater refilling and pumping of water in potential areas.
Google Translate	Effective water replenishment operations Both <u>Royal Rainmaking operations</u> groundwater recharge and pump water diversion in areas with potential

Original text	ล่าสุดเมื่อปลายเดือนตุลาคม 2566 ที่ผ่านมา <u>รองนายกฯ สมศักดิ์</u> เป็นประธานการประชุม กษช. ครั้งแรก ภายใต้รัฐบาลชุดใหม่ ได้เน้นย้ำให้หน่วยงานที่เกี่ยวข้องของบริหารจัดการทรัพยากรน้ำในช่วงฤดูแล้ง ภายใต้เงื่อนไขที่ประเทศไทยอยู่ในสภาวะเอลนีโญให้เกิดประสิทธิภาพสูงสุด โดยที่ประชุมได้พิจารณาเห็นชอบมาตรการรองรับฤดูแล้ง ปี
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	2566/2567 เพื่อรองรับสถานการณ์ดังกล่าวก่อนที่จะนำเสนอให้คณะรัฐมนตรี (ครม.) รับทราบ โดยมีทั้งหมด 9 มาตรการหลักที่สำคัญ ได้แก่
ChatGPT	In late October 2566, the NWRC held its first meeting under the new government, emphasizing the need for water-related agencies to manage water resources efficiently during the dry season of <u>2566-2567</u> . They <u>approved</u> nine significant measures, <u>including</u> :
Yandex	Recently, in late October 2018, <u>deputy prime minister Somsak</u> chaired the NBTC meeting. The first, under the new government, emphasized that the relevant agencies manage water resources during the drought under the conditions that Thailand is in the state of El Nino to maximize efficiency. the meeting approved the drought measures of <u>2018/2017</u> to accommodate the situation <u>before it was presented</u> to the Cabinet (kr.) <u>Acknowledged</u> , with a total of 9 major measures <u>including</u>
Google Translate	Most recently, at the end of October 2023, <u>Deputy Prime Minister Somsak</u> chaired the first NRC meeting under the new government. Emphasis has been placed on relevant agencies to manage water resources during the dry season. Under the conditions that Thailand is in an El Niño state for maximum efficiency. The meeting considered and approved measures to support the dry season of <u>2023/2024</u> to accommodate the said situation <u>before presenting</u> them to the Cabinet (Cabinet) <u>for acknowledgment</u> . There are a total of 9 important measures, <u>including</u> :

In addition, Yandex lags behind Google Translate in many aspects, exhibiting issues such as failing to recognize Thai characters and Thai proper names and not capitalizing them (e.g., "รองนายกฯ สมศักดิ์" translated as "deputy prime minister Somsak" or "อ่างฯ แม่งัดสมบูรณ์ชล" as "Mae kad somboonchon Basin" compared to "Mae Ngad Somboon Chol reservoir" from ChatGPT and "Mae Ngat Somboon Chon Reservoir" from Google Translate). Yandex also mishandles the conversion of Buddhist years, incorrectly rendering "2566/2567" as "2018/2017." Furthermore, Yandex appears to neglect standard English capitalization and punctuation rules, as seen in the case of "ได้แก่," which should be rendered as ", including:." In contrast, Google Translate provides a more comprehensive and accurate performance compared to Yandex. It excels in word-by-word translation, proper capitalization, recognizing and capitalizing Thai proper names, converting Buddhist years correctly, identifying sentence boundaries in Thai text, and handling tense effectively (e.g., "ก่อนที่จะนำเสนอ" correctly translated as "before presenting").

Further investigation into the mechanisms behind these tools reveals that ChatGPT relies on a large pre-trained language model that has been fine-tuned on various texts, but it does not adhere to a specific machine translation mechanism. Instead, it generates text based on patterns it has acquired during its training. On the other hand, Yandex Translate employs neural machine translation (NMT) models. Google Translate, in contrast, employs a statistical machine translation (SMT) approach, utilizing extensive parallel text data in various languages. It also incorporates neural machine translation (NMT) for certain language pairs including Thai-English.

All in all, it appears that even though both Google Translate and Yandex utilize neural machine translation (NMT) for Thai-English language pair, Google Translate demonstrates superior performance in this context. This discrepancy might be attributed to Yandex's relative weakness in handling the Thai language as a source because most of its errors stemming from the characteristics of the Thai language. In contrast, ChatGPT, despite lacking a specialized translation mechanism and skipping many parts, manages to provide translations that sound fluent and natural.

Exercise 4 Multi-reference evaluation

The output scripts can be found at

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ik9W6sYsb6T_374gBJjNAPOkRN4FgnpAyTxrwwW6Hz0/edit?usp=sharing.

Metric	Eval against Ref 1	Eval against Ref 2	Multi-Ref Evaluation
BLEU	16.3	53.7	53.9
chrF2	53.8	76.1	76.1

Based on the multi-reference evaluation, I opted for the Thai-English language pair in set B (b-th). I conducted separate evaluations against reference 1 and reference 2 to explore the impact of individual references on the overall assessment. Notably, there are discernible differences in the scores, with chrF2 consistently yielding higher scores across all evaluation scenarios (53.8 against reference 1, 76.1 against reference 2, and 76.1 in multi-evaluation compared to 16.3, 53.7, and 53.9 respectively.) Moreover, the system appears to receive notably higher assessments of both BLEU and chrF2 scores when evaluated against reference 2 (53.7 and 76.1 compared to 16.3 and 53.8 respectively).

Specifically, the gap between BLEU and chrF2 scores when assessing the system's translation with reference 1 and 2 is 37.5 and 22.4, respectively. In contrast, the difference in scores diminishes to 22.2 when employing multi-evaluation. This suggests that multi-evaluation mitigates pronounced differences, offering a more nuanced and comprehensive evaluation of the translation system's quality. Such an approach aligns with the overarching objective of utilizing multiple references: to capture the inherent variability and diversity in valid translations.

Exercise 5: Sentence-level evaluation and trained metrics

Sentence-level chrF and COMET score

Sentence	System 1		System 2		System 3		System 4	
	(chrF2)	(COMET)	(chrF2)	(COMET)	(chrF2)	(COMET)	(chrF2)	(COMET)
1	22.2	0.2868	<u>20.1</u>	0.3737	22.3	<u>0.2192</u>	24.7	0.3758
2	39.0	0.9062	40.7	0.5447	60.5	0.9455	29.5	0.6151
3	48.7	0.7398	38.0	0.2914	<u>21.2</u>	0.6744	42.8	0.4937
4	32.7	0.7989	26.9	0.3896	50.8	0.8221	41.9	0.4769
5	38.4	0.6626	28.4	0.4285	52.6	0.8386	42.1	0.6779
6	22.3	0.6466	21.9	0.4028	27.8	0.9413	21.4	0.3988
7	59.7	0.9911	56.1	0.8346	<u>81.9</u>	0.9475	60.5	0.6095
8	42.8	0.8021	30.7	0.5589	66.5	<u>0.9912</u>	60.2	0.7535
9	35.7	0.5472	42.2	0.2324	46.0	0.9325	42.8	0.7368
10	47.3	0.9522	58.6	0.6895	49.9	0.9534	40.7	0.5098
11	33.4	0.3628	42.0	0.2289	63.3	0.9836	42.4	0.3490
12	43.4	0.6765	26.7	0.3083	50.7	0.9557	40.9	0.2796
13	30.4	0.5032	28.9	<u>0.2033</u>	37.2	0.6243	43.0	0.6004

14	47.3	0.5420	37.5	0.3362	55.1	0.7079	41.2	0.4307
15	39.0	0.4754	28.8	0.4615	43.5	0.7957	33.4	0.4569
16	43.3	0.5326	31.4	0.3327	52.6	0.8824	43.0	0.6129
17	49.6	0.6873	65.1	0.9329	59.2	0.9983	46.0	0.9126
18	47.3	0.6189	33.5	0.5284	50.3	0.9195	53.0	0.6755
19	68.2	0.8607	35.2	0.2835	68.4	0.8394	65.8	0.9610
20	58.4	0.9876	55.6	0.9505	<u>77.2</u>	<u>1.0000</u>	64.3	0.5720
Average	35.8	0.71162	35.6	0.587515	54.0	0.83172	39.3	0.64431

Output scripts of chrF2 and BLEU scores can be found at
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1VmZVczcNqyz1V_rFzh_H8Ms6qXUqBxaBMoTLXJiiLy0/edit?usp=sharing

Insights from chrF2 scores

Two sentences with the highest and two with the lowest chrF2 scores across all systems (underscored in the table) are picked because the translated sentences in each system are from the same source. The sentences are listed below.

- **Score of 81.9 (System 3, Sentence 7)**
Text: The Stockmann's current negotiations concerned about 3,000 employees.
Reference: Stockmann's negotiations concerned about 3000 employees.
- **Score of 77.2 (System 3, Sentence 20)**
Text: The corrected operating profit is expected to be slightly positive this year.
Reference: The adjusted operating result is expected to be slightly positive this year.
- **Score of 20.1 (System 2, Sentence 1)**
Text: from Stockmann shots nigh 300 - sellers does not reduce
Reference: Stockmann axes up roughly 300 employees - the number of sales assistants stays the same
- **Score of 21.2 (System 3, Sentence 3)**
Text: At the start of August, the joint action companies came to an end.
Reference: The consultative negotiations in the company that has gotten into difficulties finished in the beginning of August.

The scoring of chrF2 text makes sense because the sentences with a high chrF2 score align well with the reference translation character-by-character as the name of the score suggests (chrF2). Similarly, the sentences with low chrF2 scores are very different from the reference text in terms of both order and wordings. Sentence 3 from system 3 begins the sentences with the prepositional phrase “At the start of August” while it is at the end of the reference translation, and the wording is different “in the beginning of August.”

Comparing chrF2 with COMET scores

The two sentences with the highest and lowest COMET scores are:

- **Score of 1.0000 (System 3, Sentence 20)**
Text: The corrected operating profit is expected to be slightly positive this year.
Reference: The adjusted operating result is expected to be slightly positive this year.
- **Score of 0.9912 (System 3, Sentence 8)**
Text: When they started, the need for reduction was estimated to be around 380 employees.
Reference: When they began, the need for cuts was estimated to be about 380 employees.
- **Score of 0.2033 (System 2, Sentence 13)**

- Text: Stockmann acting president's Lauri Veijalainen along sale in emporia do not reached company assign to <pl> to objectives.
- Reference: Lauri Veijalainen, the caretaker chief executive of Stockmann says that the sales performance of the department stores has continued to fall short of expectations.
- **Score of 0.2192 (System 3, Sentence 1)**

Text: Stockmann kicates almost 300 cheques - no fewer sayers

Reference: Stockmann axes up roughly 300 employees - the number of sales assistants stays the same

The COMET score emphasizes the holistic meaning of an entire sentence by incorporating semantic similarity measures. In contrast, the chrF2 score places greater emphasis on the sequence of characters within the sentences. Consequently, when comparing sentences with the lowest scores between chrF2 and COMET, it becomes evident that chrF2 evaluations are less precise. For instance, in Sentence 3 of System 3, a significant reduction in score occurs merely by relocating a prepositional phrase from the end to the beginning of the sentence and altering a word with a similar meaning. Both sentences with the lowest chrF2 score remain fairly understandable when compared to those with the lowest COMET scores.

Error detection with XCOMET-XL model

Inspecting comet_spansN.json file of System 3 as it is the best-performing system based on both chrF2 and COMET scores, the error annotations generally make sense and provide valuable insights into the quality of the translation. They highlight specific issues in the machine-generated translations, such as incorrect words, grammatical errors, and discrepancies with the reference text. The severity levels assigned to each error help assess the impact of the mistakes on the overall quality. For instance, in the first sentence, the errors indicate critical issues like the incorrect word "kicates" instead of "axes" and the phrase "no fewer sayers," which doesn't convey the intended meaning. These errors are appropriately labeled as critical, reflecting their significant impact on the translation. Similarly, in the second example, the error related to "department company" is labeled as major, emphasizing the importance of correcting this discrepancy for better accuracy.

When checking error annotations of System 2, the worst-performing system, most errors are a long section in the sentence because the translation quality of this system is low.

Overall [Extra]

	Average BLEU Score (Sentence-level)	Average chrF2 Score (Sentence-level)	Average COMET Score (Sentence-level)
System 1	12.275	35.8	0.6711
System 2	10.355	35.6	0.4876
System 3	17.65	54.0	0.8442
System 4	17.205	39.3	0.5929

System 3 is the top-performing system among the four systems, achieving the highest average scores for BLEU, chrF2, and COMET. This indicates that System 3 provides the most accurate and fluent translations. System 1, based on COMET score, comes in second place. It performs better than both System 2 and System 4, demonstrating its good translation quality. System 4 performs better than System 2 across all evaluation metrics, suggesting that it offers more accurate and fluent translations. In summary, System 3 is the most reliable for translation quality, followed by System 1, while System 4 outperforms System 2. The use of multiple evaluation metrics provides a more comprehensive view of system performance.

Assignment 2: Building parallel corpora

Part I: Collecting and aligning data

Task 1: Collect data

I initially attempted to locate my favorite movie that featured both Thai and English subtitles. However, due to the limited availability of Thai subtitles, I opted for a more well-known film, "Oppenheimer and Loki."

Task 2: Convert the subtitles to XML format

During Task 2, I encountered an issue where converting the Thai subtitles into an XML file resulted in the transformation of Thai characters into unfamiliar symbols. As a solution, I decided to choose subtitles in another language, and I opted for Spanish.

Task 3: Automatic Alignment of Movie Subtitles

The first 30 lines of English and Spanish subtitles of the films Oppenheimer and Loki applying both length-based and time-based alignment methods can be found at:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1q2642IRtms4g2H2w_EdF35tpMGtbNIPOXryvEzCFUmM/edit?usp=sharing.

Aligning the subtitles for the two languages proved to be a time-consuming task. Recognizing that the initial sections of the subtitles primarily consisted of narrations related to music and other contextual elements rather than actual speech, I shifted my focus to the latter part. Employing the length-based method with the command `uplug align/sent -src *Oppenheimer.clean.EN.xml -trg *Oppenheimer.clean.ES.xml > *Oppenheimer.clean.ENES.xml`, the alignment of subtitles appears to be accurate in terms of correct translation.

In fact, relying on the time-stamp with the code `srtalign *Oppenheimer.clean.EN.xml *Oppenheimer.clean.ES.xml > *Oppenheimer.clean.ENES.srtalign.xml`, the subtitles seem to be better aligned, especially in the first part. Length-based alignment method wrongly matches (src)="5" "(stomping intensifying)" with (trg)="4" "Y TORTURADO POR TODA LA ETERNIDAD" while the time-based method matches (src)="5" correctly with (trg)="2" "Y SE LO ENTREGÃ " A LOS HOMBRES" as demonstrated below.

(Length-based)	(Time-based)
=====	=====
(src)="5"> (stomping intensifying)	(src)="5"> (stomping intensifying)
(trg)="4"> Y TORTURADO POR TODA LA	(trg)="2"> Y SE LO ENTREGÃ " A LOS HOMBRES
ETERNIDAD	=====
=====	

Indicating LCSR threshold with `srtalign -v -c 0.7 -b *Oppenheimer.clean.EN.xml *Oppenheimer.clean.ES.xml > *Oppenheimer.clean.ENES.srtalignvc.xml`, the sample output remains the same.

I replicated the processes in Task 3 with the subtitles of the movie "Loki" and found that Loki subtitles in both English and Spanish are more straightforward with fewer circumstantial elements at the beginning. However, it is noteworthy that the time-based method tends to misalign certain sections

where the conversation overlaps. In the following example, the time-based alignment skips the translation for the English subtitle (src)="8", saying "I don't know," while the length-based method successfully retains Spanish translation (trg)="8" "No sé."

<pre>(Length-based) ===== (src)="6"> I 'm Agent Mobius , by the way (src)="7"> - How long have you been here ? (trg)="7"> Soy el agente Mobius . - ¿ Cuánto tiempo llevas aquí ? ===== (src)="8"> - I don 't know . (trg)="8"> - No sé .</pre>	<pre>(Time-based) ===== (src)="6"> I 'm Agent Mobius , by the way (src)="7"> - How long have you been here ? (src)="8"> - I don 't know . (trg)="7"> Soy el agente Mobius . - ¿ Cuánto tiempo llevas aquí ?</pre>
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Upon further inspection, it becomes apparent that the length-based method produces misalignments in several sections that are accurately aligned using the time-based method. In the provided example, where (src)="21" "They weren 't real" should correspond to (trg)="21" "No eran reales" and (src)="25" "Lamentis , The Void" to (trg)="22" "Lamentis , el Vacío," the length-based method fails to maintain these alignments. Additionally, it incorrectly arranges the Spanish translation (trg)="23" "yo he allanado el camino" before its English source (src)="27" "I paved the road" and also (trg)="21" "¡ Lo cambia todo !" coming before (src)="24" "That changes everything!" These discrepancies are not present in the time-based alignment method. It is worth noting that, in this particular context, the time-based alignment method also fails to capture the translation for (trg)="21" "¡ Lo cambia todo !", while the length-based method displays it as (src)="24" "That changes everything!", albeit with an incorrect pairing and in a reverse order.

<pre>(Length-based Method) ===== (src)="20"> You were in the Time- Keepers ' chambers . (src)="21"> - They weren 't real . (trg)="20"> Usted vio a los Guardianes del Tiempo . ===== (src)="22"> - Why 'd you think (src)="23"> - that changes anything ? (trg)="21"> No eran reales . - ¿ Crees que eso cambia algo ? - ¡ Lo cambia todo ! ===== (src)="24"> - That changes everything ! (trg)="22"> Lamentis , el Vacío . ===== (src)="25"> Lamentis , The Void . (src)="26"> Every step you took to get here , (trg)="23"> Todos esos pasos os han traído aquí porque yo he allanado el camino . ===== (src)="27"> I paved the road . (src)="28"> You kill me and destroy all this , and you don 't just have one devil , you have an infinite amount . (trg)="24"> Me matáis y destruí todo esto , y no solo tendréis a un diablo , tendréis una infinidad .</pre>	<pre>(Time-based Method) ===== (src)="21"> - They weren 't real . (src)="22"> - Why 'd you think (src)="23"> - that changes anything ? (trg)="21"> No eran reales . - ¿ Crees que eso cambia algo ? - ¡ Lo cambia todo ! ===== (src)="25"> Lamentis , The Void . (trg)="22"> Lamentis , el Vacío . ===== (src)="26"> Every step you took to get here , (src)="27"> I paved the road . (trg)="23"> Todos esos pasos os han traído aquí porque yo he allanado el camino . ===== (src)="28"> You kill me and destroy all this , and you don 't just have one devil , you have an infinite amount . (trg)="24"> Me matáis y destruí todo esto , y no solo tendréis a un diablo , tendréis una infinidad .</pre>
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Although it seems like a length-based method produces a lot more mismatches and misorders than a time-based method, given the observed strengths and weaknesses of both approaches, a strategic decision was made to adopt a hybrid approach. There is a need for adaptive strategies tailored to the

specific characteristics of the content. While the hybrid approach aims to address specific challenges in alignment, further exploration of advanced similarity metrics could potentially improve overall accuracy.

Part II: Cleaning data using OpusFilter

Task 1: Run OpusFilter with example configuration and analyze the data

100 Sample Lines from Thai and English Texts can be found at
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ImGxj7obDbtXPISQ4GXIB7rT5wm4gFZuVkJEdbmSmpg/edit?usp=sharing>.

English file contains 268244 lines, 3599247 words, and 19124160 characters.
Thai file contains 268244 lines, 943842 words, and 41225801 characters.

```
[natchsan@puhti-login14 work]$ zcat filtered.en.gz | wc
268244 3599247 19124160
[natchsan@puhti-login14 work]$ zcat filtered.th.gz | wc
268244 943842 41225801
```

After inspecting 20 sample lines, I noticed that although they contain coherent sentences in both Thai and English, covering various topics such as relationships, mathematical concepts, neuroscience, and cultural references, the content lacks naturalness and is linguistically dry. However, without a detailed examination of the entire dataset, it is challenging to definitively state whether these segments may have negative impacts on model quality.

The concern about authenticity and richness of the language stems from the fact that this database contains a large portion of mathematical expressions like “And then, you know 9% of the time you're going to get 5 heads.(sentence 6,)” “So $x - 1$ at $(x =) 1$ is going to be 0, and at $(x =) 2$, it's going to be 1 again. (sentence 38,)” and “So we get this is equal to $3x$ squared minus $2xy$ plus 2. (sentence 47).” From a quick look, out of 20 lines, around 14 sentences seem usable, the rest may sound too technical or specific.

In addition, there is a small amount of a low-quality translation that might make the model worse. For example, sentence 74 in the table below. Although the content sounds useful in training, as it can be seen from the translation provided by Google Translate, a lot of details are missing in the target translation in Thai.

Source (English)	I encourage math teachers I talk to to use multimedia, because it brings the real world into your classroom in high resolution and full color; to encourage student intuition for that level playing field; to ask the shortest question you possibly can and let those more specific questions come out in conversation; to let students build the problem, because Einstein said so; and to finally, in total, just be less helpful, because the textbook is helping you in all the wrong ways:
Target (Thai)	ผมส่งเสริมครุคณิตศาสตร์ที่ผมคุยด้วยให้ใช้สื่อประสม เพราะว่ามีสื่อช่วยปะติดปะต่อโลกภายนอกกับห้องเรียนด้วยความคมชัด และสีสดใส
Google Translate	ฉันสนับสนุนให้ครุคณิตศาสตร์ที่ผมคุยด้วยใช้มัลติมีเดีย เพราะมันจะนำโลกแห่งความเป็นจริงมาสู่ห้องเรียนของคุณด้วยความละเอียดสูงและสีที่สมบูรณ์ เพื่อส่งเสริมสัญชาตญาณของนักเรียนสำหรับสนามแข่งขันระดับนั้น ถามคำถามที่สั้นที่สุดเท่าที่จะทำได้ และปล่อยให้คำถามที่เฉพาะเจาะจงมากขึ้นออกมาในการสนทนาเพื่อให้นักเรียนสร้างปัญหาขึ้นมา เพราะอินเทอร์เน็ตกล่าวไว้เช่นนั้น และท้ายที่สุด มีประโยชน์น้อยลงเท่านั้น เพราะตำราเรียนช่วยคุณในทางที่ผิด:

Task 2: Add filters

There are several short segments in the source file that I would like to remove; for example, “OK.” (line 34) and “Right.” (line 67). These segments are not useful in training translation models. I modified the LengthFilter by changing a unit measurement from “char” for “characters” to word and setting minimum length “min_length” to 3. As a consequence, those two segments were removed.

```
- LengthFilter:  
  unit: word  
  min_length: 3  
  max_length: 5000
```

[Extra]

My initial idea was to create a custom filter to remove the mathematical segments mentioned in Task 1 because they do not represent an authentic language use. The possible filtering conditions are as follow:

1. Any segments that contain more than 2 numbers. This will cut out 8 segments from the original sample, which are:
 - line 5: I'm going to make an assumption that $1/3$ of the particles are going-- well, $1/3$ of the particles are going parallel to each of the axes.
 - line 28: We get r is equal to 0.23, or 23%.
 - line 31: And the same thing would happen here $3 \cdot 1/3$ is just 1
 - line 38: So $x - 1$ at $(x =) 1$ is going to be 0, and at $(x =) 2$, it's going to be 1 again.
 - line 47: So we get this is equal to $3x$ squared minus $2xy$ plus 2.
 - line 48: So divided by the square root of 16, which is 4, what do I get?
 - line 52: We could have figured out that this is 180 minus 56, right, which is, what?
 - line 62: Then when x is $1/5$, which is slightly further to the right, $1/5$ with $y = -2$.

This condition will mistakenly filter out 2 segments:

 - line 94: There are 800 million people starving.
 - line 95: In 2002, these centers received 45,000 animals, of which 37,000 were birds.
2. Any segments that contain more than 1 “x.” This will remove 2 segments (line 38 and line 47,) which are already filtered in step 1. There is one mistakenly filtered segment with 2 “x,” and it is relatively long: (line 25) In his singular character the dual nature alternately asserted itself, and his extreme exactness and astuteness represented, as I have often thought, the reaction against the poetic and contemplative mood which occasionally predominated in him.
3. Any segments that contain “=.” This will remove 2 lines (line 38 and line 62,) which are already filtered in step 1.
4. Any segments that contain “%.” This will cut out line 6 “And then, you know 9% of the time you're going to get 5 heads,” and line 28, which is already filtered in step 1.

Although there are 5 mathematical expressions that miss these filters (as shown below,) these filtering conditions seem to be effective in removing mathematical segments cutting out 9 lines with 3 lines wrongly affected.

- line 13: It's going from 3 to 4.
- line 30: So this whole thing can be rewritten as 3 to the third times x to the third.
- line 35: The a's and the b's.

- line 55: 2 times something minus 1.
- line 71: You could have said, hey, what happens if I go back 4 in x?

Task 3: Add duplicate removal

After checking duplicates, I identified 28 in my filtered files in both languages.

```
[natchsan@r18c03 work2]$ opusfilter-duplicates filtered.en.gz
138504it [00:00, 326378.83it/s]
Total segments: 138504
Unique segments: 136672 (98.7%)
Segments occurring once: 135248
Average number of duplicates: 1.0
Maximum number of duplicates: 28
```

```
[natchsan@r18c03 work2]$ opusfilter-duplicates filtered.th.gz
138504it [00:00, 264724.15it/s]
Total segments: 138504
Unique segments: 136906 (98.8%)
Segments occurring once: 135651
Average number of duplicates: 1.0
Maximum number of duplicates: 28
```

Therefore, in “Data processing steps”, I added the `remove_duplicates` filter before the sampling step.

```
# Run opusfilter-duplicates to remove duplicates from filtered.*.gz
- type: remove_duplicates
  parameters:
    inputs:
      - !varstr "filtered.{source}.gz"
      - !varstr "filtered.{target}.gz"
    outputs:
      - !varstr "removedup.{source}.gz"
      - !varstr "removedup.{target}.gz"
```

The duplicates were successfully removed.

```
[natchsan@r18c03 work2]$ opusfilter-duplicates sample.th.txt
100it [00:00, 90609.29it/s]
Total segments: 100
Unique segments: 100 (100.0%)
Segments occurring once: 100
Average number of duplicates: 1.0
Maximum number of duplicates: 1
```

```
[natchsan@r18c03 work2]$ opusfilter-duplicates sample.en.txt
100it [00:00, 105623.37it/s]
Total segments: 100
Unique segments: 100 (100.0%)
Segments occurring once: 100
Average number of duplicates: 1.0
Maximum number of duplicates: 1
```

The updated script with `remove_duplicates` filter can be found at

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ukhZeKmf2C_Log7P0WisRIO_0g8l-c4BvIsgLqZkoDE/edit?usp=sharing.

Assignment 3: Introduction to OpenNMT-py

Exercise 0: Get the data

I chose to use English as a target language and other three as sources.

Exercise 1: Learning and applying subword segmentation

Examining the image captions, I did not find a lot of specific terms or rare words, and although the dataset is not large, I prefer to preserve the entire words in translation. Therefore, I keep the BPE (Byte Pair Encoding) instead of the Unigram tokenization model. After using the model files to segment the training, test, and validation files, the output encoded files of all languages contain a correct number of lines: 29000 in training, 1000 in test, and 1014 in validation files.

```
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l train.bpe.en
29000 train.bpe.en
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l test.bpe.en
1000 test.bpe.en
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l val.bpe.en
1014 val.bpe.en
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l train.bpe.de
29000 train.bpe.de
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l test.bpe.de
1000 test.bpe.de
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l val.bpe.de
1014 val.bpe.de

[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l train.bpe.fr
29000 train.bpe.fr
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l test.bpe.fr
1000 test.bpe.fr
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l val.bpe.fr
1014 val.bpe.fr
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l train.bpe.cs
29000 train.bpe.cs
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l test.bpe.cs
1000 test.bpe.cs
[natchsan@puhti-login11 multi30k]$ wc -l val.bpe.cs
1014 val.bpe.cs
```

Exercise 2: Data conversion

With adjustments of training and validation paths for each language pair in config_vocab.yaml file, I have produced 6 files of 3 language pairs as follow: German-English (1920 and 1904 unique tokens respectively,) French-English (1921 and 1904 unique tokens respectively,) and Czech-English (1948 and 1904 unique tokens respectively).

```
[natchsan@puhti-login12 assignment3]$ nano config_vocab.yaml
[natchsan@puhti-login12 assignment3]$ onmt_build_vocab -config ./config_vocab.yaml
Corpus multi30k's weight should be given. We default it to 1 for you.
[2023-11-23 18:41:57,750 INFO] Counter vocab from 5000 samples.
[2023-11-23 18:41:57,750 INFO] Build vocab on 5000 transformed examples/corpus.
[2023-11-23 18:41:57,774 INFO] multi30k's transforms: TransformPipe()
[2023-11-23 18:41:58,115 INFO] Counters src:1920
[2023-11-23 18:41:58,115 INFO] Counters tgt:1904

[natchsan@puhti-login12 assignment3]$ nano config_vocab.yaml
[natchsan@puhti-login12 assignment3]$ onmt_build_vocab -config ./config_vocab.yaml
Corpus multi30k's weight should be given. We default it to 1 for you.
[2023-11-23 18:43:57,047 INFO] Counter vocab from 5000 samples.
[2023-11-23 18:43:57,047 INFO] Build vocab on 5000 transformed examples/corpus.
[2023-11-23 18:43:57,071 INFO] multi30k's transforms: TransformPipe()
[2023-11-23 18:43:57,266 INFO] Counters src:1921
[2023-11-23 18:43:57,267 INFO] Counters tgt:1904

[natchsan@puhti-login12 assignment3]$ nano config_vocab.yaml
[natchsan@puhti-login12 assignment3]$ onmt_build_vocab -config ./config_vocab.yaml
Corpus multi30k's weight should be given. We default it to 1 for you.
[2023-11-23 18:45:18,880 INFO] Counter vocab from 5000 samples.
[2023-11-23 18:45:18,880 INFO] Build vocab on 5000 transformed examples/corpus.
```

```
[2023-11-23 18:45:18,899 INFO] multi30k's transforms: TransformPipe()  
[2023-11-23 18:45:19,146 INFO] Counters src:1948  
[2023-11-23 18:45:19,146 INFO] Counters tgt:1904
```

Exercise 3: Training

After modifying file paths in the config.yaml file and specifying my email address in the example.sh file, I submitted the Slurm jobs with the following ID corresponding to each language pair: 19485017 for German-English, 19485064 for French-English, and 19485067 for Czech-English. The progresses of the machine translation training using a neural machine translation (NMT) model with the OpenNMT-py library of the three language pairs are as follow:

	Step	Accuracy (%)	Perplexity*
German-English			*The lower, the better
	50/10000	14.68	365.18
	2000/10000	40.92	18.03
	4000/10000	46.04	12.37
	6000/10000	52.77	8.48
	8000/10000	53.02	8.30
	10000/10000	56.35	6.98
French-English			
	50/10000	13.75	377.66
	2000/10000	41.13	17.70
	4000/10000	47.85	11.61
	6000/10000	57.20	6.97
	8000/10000	59.81	6.10
	10000/10000	63.39	5.05
Czech-English			
	50/10000	14.68	328.84
	2000/10000	42.69	16.67
	4000/10000	50.49	10.31
	6000/10000	46.82	17.911
	8000/10000	46.99	17.403
	10000/10000	46.99	17.911

The outputs from the training model can be found at <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1JBZK8CHpSSV0consptq4NWrMBuSToPSMG8D5LWkmKHY/edit?usp=sharing>.

- Questions: How does the validation perplexity progress over time? How does the validation accuracy progress over time?
- In the overall assessment of the training progress presented in the table, notable advancements are observed in both accuracy and perplexity metrics within the initial 2000 steps of the training process. Subsequently, these metrics of German and French to English language pairs gradually improve as the training approaches its conclusion while those of Czech to English degrade after step 6000/10000.

A significant enhancement in accuracy of the first two language pairs is evident, progressing from approximately 14% at step 50 to around 40% at step 2000, ultimately reaching around 60% at step 10000. Pertaining to perplexity, lower values signify heightened certainty and precision in

predicting sequences. The perplexity values on the validation set for all language pairs exhibit a substantial improvement from step 50 to 2000, jumping from around 350 to 16. After that, German and French to English language pairs see a gradual improvement from 18.03 and 17.70 to 6.98 and 5.05 respectively. Czech to English, on the other hand, after a slight improvement from 16.67 at step 2000 to 10.31 at step 4000, it swung up to around 17 towards the end. Overall, the best model translation is for the French-English language pair, followed by German-English and Czech-English respectively.

Exercise 4: Testing

To translate the source to target language, I selected the model of step 10000 because the accuracy and the perplexity of the training models reach the peak for German-English and French-English while Czech-English exhibits acceptable fluctuations. The Slurm jobs corresponding to each language pair have the following IDs: 19485072 for German-English, 19485084 for French-English, and 19485131 for Czech-English. This produces 3 English translation files from the German, French, and Czech source languages. To prevent confusion, I named the files test_pred.bpe.de_en, test_pred.bpe.fr_en, and test_pred.bpe.cs_en. Observing the BPE-encoded files, I found 9 <unk> for German-English, 8 for French-English, and 3 for Czech-English. After converting them into translation files, <unk> became "??." The translation files seem a little easier to read. Below are all the sentences with <unk> in the BPE-encoded files.

The decoded BPE-encoded files with <unk> can be found at

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CwAq8JtareaLIMF_k6qebwHY0-oyOYZIxMMsPikKK6k/edit?usp=sharing.

(German-English)

1. _A _old _man _is _talking _to _a _woman _who _is _wearing _a _blue _t - shirt _that _says _" <unk> "
2. _A _man _walking _down _the _street _past _a _L o n d o n _2 <unk> at .
3. _People _running _a _race _in _a <unk> .
4. _A _man _standing _on _the _street _holding _a _sign _that _says _" s <unk> a " .
5. _An _old _man _walking _down _the _street _past _a _L o n d o n _l e d _B M <unk> .
6. _Two <unk> ers , _one _with _a _bike , _are _riding _their _bikes _on _the _street _while _the _crowd _watches _them .
7. _The _man _with _the _number _ <unk> _on _his _hat _is _riding _a _bike .
8. _A _p u p p y _wearing _white _is _playing _with _the _number _ <unk> _on _his _surfboard .
9. _A _line _of _spectators , _with _the _number _ <unk> _t a c k l e _o p p o n e n t _and _the _red _team .

(French-English)

1. _A _man _walking _down _the _street _with _a <unk>
2. _A _cowboy _is _riding _a _B M <unk> _bike _rider _in _midair .
3. _The _football _player _wearing _the _number _ <unk> _t a g s _his _o p p o n e n t _with _the _ball .
4. _A _group _of _men _and _a _woman _are _running _in _a <unk> .
5. _A _man _on _a _motorcycle _riding _a _dirt _bike _r a c e r _in _the _number _ <unk> .
6. _A _cowboy _is _riding _a _B M <unk> _bike _rider _in _midair .
7. _A _lot _of _people _are _singing _into <unk> _p h o n e s _in _the _middle _of _the _street .
8. _A _B M <unk> _r a c e r _rides _his _board _in _the _middle _of _the _ocean .

(Czech-English)

1. _C h e e r l e a d e r s _in _a _r e <unk> d i n g _s t u d i o .
2. _Two _men , _one _with _a _football , _one _with _the _number _ <unk> _is _about _to _run _in _a _game _of _soccer .
3. _Two _women _are _j o g g i n g _on _a _p a t i e n t _and _r e <unk> d i n g _a _building .

- Questions: Do you observe any <unk> in the BPE-encoded output? Why/why not? If so, how is <unk> represented in the decoded output?
- <unk> represents unknown or out-of-vocabulary words. Comparing the translation to the source language file, I found that <unk> occurs because the source language segments are foreign to the translation model. In other words, the model has never seen the segments before.

Next, I replaced '_' with space and removed space in the beginning of the sentences to use them as translation files to calculate BLEU and ChrF2 scores. The scores are as follow:

	BLEU	ChrF2
German-English	11.3	27.6
French-English	18.8	35.0
Czech-English	14.6	31.8

The output script of BLEU and ChrF2 scores of the translation from the three language pairs can be found at <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1tt7NxdIX9Qjj4G25bhEtsPDGPatqs17m8QZt1GIRqsl/edit?usp=sharing>.

- Questions: How do the scores vary according to the source language? Does the ranking correspond to your expectations? Look at the output of the three models. Remember that the same amount of data (and the same sentences) are used for all language pairs, the only difference is the source language.
- The evaluation of translation quality based on BLEU and chrF2 scores is partly consistent with the conclusion drawn from the accuracy and perplexity metrics. Even though the accuracy and perplexity metrics suggested German-English and French-English translations were of higher quality, the external evaluation with BLEU and chrF2 scores revealed a different ranking, with French-English still being the best, but Czech-English surpassing German-English.

It is worth noting that BLEU and chrF2 scores provide a more direct assessment of the translation performance while accuracy and perplexity scores measure the correctness and uncertainty of a translation model. Moreover, the reference translation in this BLEU and chrF2 score calculations is not a gold standard or human translation.

Exercise 5: Examining the training process

To assess translation quality across various models at 2000-step intervals, I selected the French-English language pair. This choice was motivated by the observation that it demonstrated superior translation quality with the model at the final step when compared to the other two language pairs, allowing for a clear and contrasting evaluation. [EXTRA] The BLEU and chrF2 scores of each step interval are as follow:

Step	BLEU	chrF2
2000	2.8	18.9
4000	4.7	20.9
6000	10.4	27.2
8000	15.0	32.0
10000	18.5	35.0

The output script of BLEU and chrF2 scores of Each Step Interval of French-English translation can be found at https://docs.google.com/document/d/1_yuhFe_0k7ojDliVl07xh2WfryWmRq0Ms5rZs2EAO6Y/edit?usp=sharing.

The translations using the model from step 2000 compared with step 10000 are shown below.

Step 2000

1. A man and a woman are walking down the street .
2. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in front of a crowd of people .
3. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in the snow .
4. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is playing the guitar while another man watches .
5. A group of people are walking in the snow .
6. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is playing the guitar while another man watches .
7. A man and a woman are walking down the street .
8. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is playing the guitar while another man watches .
9. A man is walking in the snow .
10. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in the snow .
11. A man in a red jacket is walking in the snow .
12. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is playing the guitar while another man watches .
13. A man and a woman are walking down the street .
14. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in the snow .
15. A man and a woman are walking down the street .
16. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in front of a crowd of people .
17. A man in a red jacket is walking in the snow .
18. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in front of a crowd of people .
19. A man in a red jacket is walking in the snow .
20. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in the snow .
21. A man is walking in the snow .
22. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in the snow .
23. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in the snow .
24. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in the snow .
25. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in the snow .
26. A man in a red jacket and blue jeans is walking in the snow .
27. A man and a woman are walking down the street .

Step 10000

1. A man in an orange shirt looking to his right .
2. A middle - aged blond male brunette woman sitting on the grass .
3. A girl in a black outfit is playing with a soccer ball .
4. Five people in snow shoes are standing in snow and snow shoes along the shore .
5. People are using spray paint on a mountain .
6. A man in a hard hat is standing with a woman who is listening to music on a street corner , while a woman stands by .
7. A group of people standing in front of an audience .
8. A boy in red swim trunks gets ready to hit the golf ball towards the camera as he plays baseball .
9. A guy is working on a building .
10. A man in a green vest is sitting on the ground holding a sign .
11. A mother and daughter tending to be working .
12. Men playing volleyball with the ball , and there are playing for the ball .
13. A woman holding flowers is eating in a kitchen .
14. A man sitting at a table eating a bowl of food .
15. Three people are sitting in a vehicle .
16. A girl in a dress walks down a cobblestone sidewalk .
17. A blond headed person laying in the grass .
18. A woman with a black and red dress talking to another man on a bicycle .
19. The person in the swimming pool is taking a picture .
20. Two men are shaking hands while other people look on .
21. People standing in front of a building .
22. A teenager is playing for the ball on the shore .
23. A woman does a jump on a sand sculpture on the beach .
24. A man is standing next to a woman who is working on a train .
25. A woman is looking up at an exhibit .
26. A woman in a purple dress , and a young girl in a striped shirt .
27. A man trying to climb up a cliff .
28. A group of Asian people are playing musical instruments for the camera .

Full translations of French-English models from step 2000, 6000, and 10000 can be found at

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1xDjPD3SMUabOwrSi-2CoBbeY_Gx3zSipAlp9QuqB38/edit?usp=sharing.

- Question: What do the translations look like with the first model? Can you spot clear improvements in translation quality over time?
- It is evident that the model at step 2000 generates several similar translations (sentence 20 and 22-28). In contrast, the model at step 10000 captures more intricate details and nuances in the sentences, resulting in significantly improved translations. Comparing the translation of sentence 1 which is “A man in an orange hat staring at something.” from the reference test.en file. The step-2000 model translates the French source sentence “Un homme avec un chapeau orange regardant quelque chose.” as “A man and a woman are walking down the street.” while it is “A man in an orange shirt looking to his right.” for the step-10000 model. The translation from the model at step 6000 offers a middle-quality translation: “A man in a white shirt is singing into a microphone.” This shows an improvement in translation quality over time. Step 10000 model correctly translates the subject “Un homme avec un chapeau orange” as “A man in an orange shirt.” Step 6000 model offers a closer translation as “A man in a white shirt,” and step 2000 model produces the furthest meaning “A man and a woman.” It is the same for the latter part of the sentence with “looking to his

right” of the step 10000 model being the closest to the reference followed by “singing into a microphone” of step 6000 and “walking down the street” of step 2000.

Exercise 6: Modifying the network parameter

For this experiment, I opted to use the French-English language pair for consistency. In configuring the parameters in the ‘config.yaml’ file, my hypothesis centered on the belief that the size of the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) would wield the most significant influence on both model performance and translation quality. To test this hypothesis, I adjusted the RNN size from 256 to 512 (Slurm Job ID: 19487395). Subsequently, recognizing that larger word vector sizes can enhance the model's capacity to capture nuanced meanings, I increased the word vector size from 256 to 512 (Slurm Job ID: 19487424). Finally, in an exploration of the impact of layer depth, I raised the number of layers from 1 to 5 (Slurm Job ID: 19487318). I computed BLEU and chrF2 scores for the models at both step 8000 and 10000 to examine whether closely-performed models, with the expectation that the model at step 10000 would outperform the one at step 8000, deliver translation quality in a similar manner.

	Accuracy (%)	Perplexity*	BLEU/chrF2 Scores
		*The lower, the better	
Original Parameters	63.39	5.05	18.8/35.0
Increased RNN from 256 to 512			
50/10000	14.42	397.86	
2000/10000	42.41	16.08	
4000/10000	52.20	8.69	
6000/10000	58.82	6.03	
8000/10000	60.24	5.62	14.1/31.5
10000/10000	61.84	5.31	11.0/27.1
Increased vector size from 256 to 512			
50/10000	15.15	382.09	
2000/10000	41.99	17.19	
4000/10000	50.49	10.10	
6000/10000	59.27	6.29	
8000/10000	62.19	5.40	16.6/34.3
10000/10000	64.56	4.75	17.6/35.4
Increased layers from 1 to 5			
50/10000	8.53	536.69	
2000/10000	29.81	49.59	
4000/10000	34.18	29.79	
6000/10000	39.82	19.33	
8000/10000	43.43	14.72	5.8/23.3
10000/10000	44.50	13.52	6.9/24.9

The model training outputs after parameter adjustment and related BLEU and ChrF2 scores can be found at <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HOSKNrGJCQrr7va5OjcZSdgsYyGnZKe2ipFEI4E2854/edit?usp=sharing>.

- Questions: Do you observe any impact on translation quality? Which parameter influences translation quality most?

- **Step 10000 model:**

Modifying the RNN size from 256 to 512 yields a marginal decrease in performance, as evidenced by a decline in accuracy and perplexity from 63.39 and 5.05 (without parameter adjustments) to 61.84 and 5.31, respectively. Furthermore, BLEU and ChrF2 scores also experience a reduction from 18.8 and 35.0 to 11.0 and 27.1, respectively.

It is noteworthy that, unlike alterations to the other two parameters, the vector size exerts the most pronounced influence on both the translation model and translation quality. This impact, surprisingly, exceeds that of the original configuration. A larger vector size contributes to heightened accuracy and perplexity, elevating the model's metrics from 63.39 and 5.05 to 64.56 and 4.75, respectively. Meanwhile, BLEU and ChrF2 scores closely align with the original parameters, registering at 17.6 and 35.4, compared to 18.8 and 35.0, respectively.

The introduction of additional layers results in a notably slower improvement, with accuracy showing only a slight increase over time—from 8.53 to 44.50. Similarly, perplexity experiences a gradual enhancement from 536.69 to 13.52. Consequently, even the optimal model from this parameter adjustment yields a low-quality translation, as evidenced by BLEU and ChrF2 scores of only 6.9 and 24.9, respectively. This marks a significant decline from the baseline scores of 18.8 and 35.0 observed with just one layer.

- **Step 8000 model:**

In the evaluation of translation quality between the models at steps 8000 and 10000, adjustments to vector size and layer parameters exhibit a slightly diminished performance, in accordance with the expectation (16.6 and 34.3, compared to 17.6 and 35.4 for vector size increment; and 5.8 and 23.3, compared to 6.9 and 24.9 for additional layers, respectively). However, with an increase in RNN layers, the model at step 8000 marginally outperforms the one at step 10000, recording scores of 14.1 and 31.5, compared to 11.0 and 27.1, respectively.

In this assignment, I have learned various aspects of training neural machine translation models using OpenNMT-py. I went through the processes of data collection, subword segmentation, data conversion, training, testing, and examined the impact of modifying network parameters. Notably, the vector size parameter emerged as the key factor influencing translation quality. This assignment provided valuable insights into the nuances of training NMT models and their performance evaluation.

Assignment 4: NMT with attention

Exercise 1: Choose a language pair and data set

For this assignment, I chose Europarl corpus. My language pair is German - English. In the preprocess steps, I also removed duplicates from the data. After preprocessing the dataset, I ended up with 1916659 lines, 45428582 words, and 334213764 characters for German language and 1916659 lines, 48782648 words, and 292408468 for English.

```
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ wc removedup.de.txt
1916659 45428582 334213764 removedup.de.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ wc removedup.en.txt
1916659 48782648 292408468 removedup.en.txt
```

Then, I split the corpus datasets (removedup.de.txt and removedup.en.txt) into three sets: a training set, a validation set, and a test set. The test and the validation set contain 5000 lines each, and the rest belong to the train set. I make sure that the lines in the three sets do not overlap by shuffling the lines in the corpus before splitting it into three sets. A number of lines, words, and characters of the three sets in both German and English language are shown in the table below.

File	Number of Lines	Number of Sentences	Number of Characters
train_source.txt	1,906,659	45,192,943	332,480,539
train_target.txt	1,906,659	48,528,885	290,888,254
val_source.txt	5,000	118,217	869,244
val_target.txt	5,000	126,872	759,985
test_source.txt	5,000	117,422	863,981
test_target.txt	5,000	126,891	760,229

```
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ source_corpus="removedup.de.txt"
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ target_corpus="removedup.en.txt"
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ validation_lines=5000
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ test_lines=5000
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ paste -d'\t' "$source_corpus" "$target_corpus" | shuf | awk -F'\t'
'{print $1 > "shuffled_source.txt"; print $2 > "shuffled_target.txt"}'
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ total_lines=$(wc -l < shuffled_source.txt)
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ train_lines=$((total_lines - validation_lines - test_lines))
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ head -n "$train_lines" shuffled_source.txt > train_source.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ head -n "$train_lines" shuffled_target.txt > train_target.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ tail -n +"$((train_lines + 1))" shuffled_source.txt | head -n
"$validation_lines" > val_source.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ tail -n +"$((train_lines + 1))" shuffled_target.txt | head -n
"$validation_lines" > val_target.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ tail -n +"$((train_lines + validation_lines + 1))"
shuffled_source.txt | head -n "$test_lines" > test_source.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ tail -n +"$((train_lines + validation_lines + 1))"
shuffled_target.txt | head -n "$test_lines" > test_target.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ rm shuffled_source.txt shuffled_target.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ wc train_source.txt
1906659 45192943 332480539 train_source.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ wc train_target.txt
1906659 48528885 290888254 train_target.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ wc val_source.txt
5000 118217 869244 val_source.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ wc val_target.txt
5000 126872 759985 val_target.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ wc test_source.txt
5000 117422 863981 test_source.txt
[natchsan@puhti-login11 data]$ wc test_target.txt
5000 126891 760229 test_target.txt
```

To prevent confusion and be more specific, I renamed the files to test_de, test_en, train_de, train_en, val_de, and val_en accordingly.

Exercise 2: Subword segmentation

Using the spm_train tool from the SentencePiece library to train the Byte Pair Encoding (BPE) models for all sets of both languages, I ended up having the following models in the working directory.

```
spmmodel_test_en.model   spmmodel_train_en.model   spmmodel_val_en.model  
spmmodel_test_en.vocab   spmmodel_train_en.vocab   spmmodel_val_en.vocab  
spmmodel_test_de.model   spmmodel_train_de.model   spmmodel_val_de.model  
spmmodel_test_de.vocab   spmmodel_train_de.vocab   spmmodel_val_de.vocab
```

Then, I applied these trained SentencePiece models to tokenize the relevant datasets, which produced six BPE-encoded files of the training, validation, and test sets of both German and English as shown below.

```
test_bpe_de.txt   train_bpe_de.txt   val_bpe_de.txt  
test_bpe_en.txt   train_bpe_en.txt   val_bpe_en.txt
```

Exercise 3: Train models

In this step, I started with creating vocabulary files which contain a list of unique tokens along with their frequencies. There are three types of models: RNNnoattention, RNNwithattention, and transformer. In the RNNwithattention.yaml file, I adjusted the global_attention parameter to "dot." This resulted in six vocab files with frequencies: two from each model (one from the source and another from the target language.)

```
vocab.RNNnoattention.de_en.src   vocab.RNNwithattention.de_en.src   vocab.transformer.de_en.src  
vocab.RNNnoattention.de_en.tgt   vocab.RNNwithattention.de_en.tgt   vocab.transformer.de_en.tgt
```

Next, I created three SLURM scripts and trained the models.

The SLURM job id for the transformer model is 19553145.

The SLURM job id for the RNN model with attention is 19553144.

The SLURM job id for the RNN model without attention is 19553656.

During the model training, I noticed that the RNN model with attention took the longest time (06:13:55 hours) followed by the RNN model without attention (05:07:41 hours) and the transformer model (04:25:03 hours.) With the keep_checkpoint set to 3 in the .yaml file, only the last 3 models are outputted, which are the ones in step 30000, 40000, and 50000. This resulted in 9 models as follow:

```
RNNnoattention_de_en_step_30000.pt   RNNwithattention_de_en_step_30000.pt   transformer_de_en_step_30000.pt  
RNNnoattention_de_en_step_40000.pt   RNNwithattention_de_en_step_40000.pt   transformer_de_en_step_40000.pt  
RNNnoattention_de_en_step_50000.pt   RNNwithattention_de_en_step_50000.pt   transformer_de_en_step_50000.pt
```

Exercise 4: Test and compare

After applying the models to the test file, test_bpe_en.txt, and decoding the translated .bpe files, I found that there were still some “_” symbols left from the .bpe file. Therefore, I replaced them with a space before calculating BLEU and chrF2 scores.

rejected by the end of the year.
 To put it mildly, I would like to say that I voted against the motion for a resolution by Mr de Roo.
 I would like to say that, in the end, the President-in-Office of the Council, Mr President-in-Office of the Council, is not in favour of the motion for a resolution, which was rejected by the President of the European Parliament.
 Ladies and gentlemen, I would like to conclude by saying that the motion for a resolution tabled by the Committee on Economic and Monetary Affairs and Industrial Policy is a step backwards.
 I should like to conclude by saying that I do not agree with the vote on the motion for a resolution, which was postponed to the end of the year.
 I should like to say that I am very happy to vote in favour of the motion for a resolution, which is a very short time ago.
 Mr President, ladies and gentlemen, I would like to conclude by saying that I am very pleased to be able to vote in favour of the motion for a resolution, but also to the end of the year, which was voted on by the Council and the Commission.

BLEU and chrF2 scores of the test set are shown in the table and the chart below.

Models	BLEU	chrF2
RNN without attention step 30000	21.5	46.6
RNN without attention step 40000	23.2	48.4
RNN without attention step 50000	23.9	49.0
RNN with attention step 30000	28.7	54.0
RNN with attention step 40000	29.6	54.8
RNN with attention step 50000	29.9	55.0
Transformer step 30000	31.9	56.6
Transformer step 40000	32.5	56.9
Transformer step 50000	32.4	56.8

BLEU and chrF2 Scores of the Test Set

The outputs of BLEU and chrF2 scores of the test set can be found at

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1togEBa7xu3VJ0f4KyPhv5Mu-Q1fiaYhbZo6oUR4lr6s/edit?usp=sharing>.

[Extra]

I applied the same set of models to the validation set, val_bpe_de.txt. After getting the decoded .bpe translations and removing the remaining “_” symbols, I calculated BLEU and chrF2 scores of the validation set translations against the reference translation, val_en.txt. The scores are as follow:

Models	BLEU	chrF2
RNN without attention step 30000	2.0	19.2
RNN without attention step 40000	1.6	16.3
RNN without attention step 50000	1.6	15.7
RNN with attention step 30000	2.0	17.2
RNN with attention step 40000	1.0	12.5
RNN with attention step 50000	1.4	13.6
Transformer step 30000	2.4	21.0
Transformer step 40000	2.2	19.5
Transformer step 50000	2.0	17.2

BLEU and chrF2 Scores of the Validation and the Test Set

The outputs of BLEU and chrF2 scores of the validation set can be found at https://docs.google.com/document/d/1_OmyAlIz18eLcbEclq4-B8OTE1VHHHRG1wuMkOCwy48/edit?usp=sharing.

From the comparison table, the scores of the validation set are significantly lower than the test set. After examining both sets, I found that the content and language used in the two sets are quite different. The validation set contains sentences that are longer and delve into legal and procedural matters, requiring a deep understanding of European institutions and policies. The language in the validation set also appears more formal and technical. This disparity in the length, language complexity, and topic diversity could contribute to the differences in BLEU and chrF2 scores between the two sets. Considering that RNN models often suffer from the vanishing gradient problem, where

gradients diminish as they are backpropagated through time, it makes sense to see the drop of translation quality of RNN models on the validation set, which contains longer sentences.

Transformers do not have this issue since they process the entire sequence simultaneously. To improve model performance on the validation set, additional training data covering diverse topics and language complexities may be beneficial. Below are the sample lines from test and validation sets.

Sample lines from the test set are as follow:

1. You all know that the airlines make most profit on the North Atlantic route and not on internal European routes.
2. Arms export must form an integral part of the new EU security policy.
3. Mr President, the EU is the reason for the long journey times for animals.
4. I have supported unreservedly the excellent work carried out in the Committee on Development and Cooperation.
5. The question is whether this long wait is desirable.
6. The content of the proposal - from a purely legalistic point of view - is limited.
7. Not only, therefore, have they not succeeded in ensuring that the cut-off date of 31 December 2001 was met, a date which they themselves had fixed, but they have just granted a scandalous new time limit, namely the end of 2005.
8. In short, it is a precaution for ships that have shown a number of weaknesses when controls were carried out.
9. Furthermore, it is of decisive importance that we are today developing long-term strategies, that we are in a position to make joint plans and that both sides know what our common interests will be in 10 or 20 years' time, so that we can base our practical policy on them.
10. I am delighted to hear that the Commission is to follow up the Committee's initiative by bringing forward a proposal for a legislative instrument concerning the good governance of collecting societies.
11. What it boils down to is that there is not enough start-up capital available for people who want to set up in business, and so numerous young entrepreneurs have to give up again prematurely.
12. People inhabit them and make their public education, health and transport services, their trade and industry, and their cultural activities work.
13. To give support to voluntary work and enhance social recognition, it is important that a community of purpose is created, with transfer of best practice and experience by the active players - government, business, trade unions and voluntary organisations - working together in dialogue and in partnership.
14. Does the European Union then not have sufficient weight and influence to convince its partner, Morocco, of the mutual advantages of signing the new agreement?
15. One of the key priorities is to strengthen public policies aimed at ensuring that equal rights are effectively upheld.

Sample lines from the validation set are as follow:

1. Madam President, Commissioner, the report presented by the rapporteur represents a real step forward, just as the package of measures put forward by the Commission has finally succeeded in stirring up the tax debate at European level.
2. EU involvement is not only in its interests but also in our own and, given our comprehensive and coherent approach, it is only logical that the EU has taken over the NATO operation.
3. Whilst awaiting the outcome of the compatibility assessment under the public procurement rules, and in application of the 'precautionary principle', some of the payments, namely those linked to the TEN-T budget line, have been suspended.
4. . The report under discussion recommends that the EU Member States ratify the European Constitution.
5. I have to say that during the Convention, in which I was proud to take part as an alternate member, I respected - though I did not always agree with - the positions taken by the United Kingdom Government representatives.
6. If we do not act and tackle the barriers that undermine the potential of European industry, then the European citizen will pay the price not only in terms of slower economic growth and lower employment opportunities, but also in terms of cultural and social influence.
7. If one party does not keep to an agreement, is it not natural for the other party to cancel the agreement, since the agreement concerns mutual obligations?
8. In fact, working on this basis we could imagine too that in the future new agreements could be made with companies.
9. It is bad enough that the European Parliament has not made time to debate the situation until today, but it is even worse that the European Commission has shown itself totally lacking in initiative and that the Council has been unable to adopt any decisions on the matter.
10. The difference between the two is that my proposal would grant every Member State that is not able to prepare itself in time, or that runs into other obstacles, the possibility of a derogation.
11. What initiatives will the Presidency take to achieve its objective of correct and responsible

- implementation of the Stability Pact and where has it identified the difficulties so far in correctly implementing it?
12. In the summer, President Karzai was elected by an Emergency Loya Jirga to lead the Afghanistan Transitional Authority; constitutional and judicial commissions have been established; a new currency has been introduced, and the process of recovery and of reconstruction is well under way with increasingly strong leadership from the Afghan Government.
 13. The introduction of such a reduced period for implementing powers - much shorter than the normal period of four years - clearly emphasizes the need urgently to find a solid, lasting and balanced solution for the supervision of the Commission's implementing powers by both branches of the legislative authority.
 14. People are getting worked up about particular cases just now, but what is far more serious is that we do not have a reliable overview of the scale, nature and results of the suspected internal cases investigated by the Commission.
 15. Moldova's need for finance will be huge in the years to come.

Discussions

- Do the BLEU and chrF scores increase by using attention? What about comparing RNNs -> RNNs with attention -> Transformer?
 - BLEU and chrF scores generally increase when transitioning from RNN with no attention to RNN with attention, and further to Transformer. The attention mechanism helps the model focus on relevant parts of the input sequence, improving translation quality.
- What is the impact of the attention mechanism on BLEU and chrF scores?
 - The attention mechanism has a positive impact on BLEU and chrF scores. As attention mechanisms allow the model to focus on specific parts of the input sequence during translation, they enhance the model's ability to capture long-range dependencies and improve translation accuracy.
- How is the accuracy performance in the development set (also called validation set) for 1 model across different checkpoint, and how does this compare to the test set results?
 - To answer this question, I chose to analyze the best performing model, the transformer model. To test its performance, I compared it with the worst performing model, the RNN model without attention. The accuracy scores at each step of the two models are as follow:

Model	Step	Accuracy (%)
RNN without attention	30000/50000	54.16
RNN without attention	40000/50000	56.07
RNN without attention	50000/50000	57.38
Transformer	30000/50000	68.03
Transformer	40000/50000	69.09
Transformer	50000/50000	69.78

Training Outputs of RNN Model without Attention and Transformer Model can be found at https://docs.google.com/document/d/1nnzWJyE9NTQSVgnUZx-4jL_Fhzf_NXHt1mdEfonryoKY/edit?usp=sharing.

The accuracy scores of the RNN model without attention exhibited a gradual improvement over the course of training, yet they consistently remained lower than the corresponding scores of the transformer model. Although the transformer model displayed a similar trend in its accuracy scores, they demonstrated closer proximity to each other. In summary, the accuracy scores of both models align with their respective translation quality; the RNN model without attention consistently yielded lower translation quality compared to the transformer model.

- Do the scores match with the intuitions that you get by inspecting the translations in the output files?
- The BLEU and chrF2 scores effectively capture the translation quality disparities between the worst-performing model, the RNN model without attention at step 30000, and the best-performing model, the transformer model at step 50000. I added a translation from the RNN model with attention at step 50000 as a reference point to see the gradient of improvement.

Reference:

You all know that the airlines make most profit on the North Atlantic route and not on internal European routes.

RNN model without attention step 30000:

You are all aware that the airlines are the most vulnerable in terms of purchasing power and not at European airports.

RNN model with attention step 50000:

You are all aware that the airlines are making most profits on the eCall and not on intra-European routes.

Transformer model step 50000:

You all know that the airlines make most of the profits, not on intra-European routes.

Examining the predicative part of the subordinating clause and the prepositional phrase at the end of the sentence reveals crucial insights. In the RNN model without attention at step 30000, there is a failure to capture the meaning of the predicative part, translating it as "are the most vulnerable" instead of "make most profit." Similarly, the prepositional phrase is inaccurately translated as "at European airports" instead of "on internal European routes." In contrast, the RNN model with attention at step 50000 and the Transformer model at step 50000 provide very similar translations for both the predicative and prepositional phrase, accurately rendering "are making most profits," "make most of the profits" and "on intra-European routes," "on intra-European routes," respectively. The only tiny difference is the aspect of tense, with the RNN model with attention using the present continuous tense compared to the present simple tense in the source translation.

- Look at the *.err files produced when you submitted the job translating the test set with the RNN model with attention (from this week's exercise 4, section 3b). These files contain the attention weight matrices for each translated sentence. Select 5 (preferably short) sentences and analyze the corresponding attention matrices. Do they match your expectations?
- To analyze the attention matrices for the translated sentences, I examined the .err file produced during the translation of the test set. Below are the five sentences I chose from the .err file. Note that the "*" symbol marks the maximum attention weight in each row, indicating which English word has the highest attention weight for the corresponding German word.

```
[2023-11-30 00:28:57,695 INFO]
_The 0.1708541 0.1380055 *0.1719714 0.1630608 0.1667166 0.0926782 0.0269639 0.0263963 0.0088722 0.0176034 0.0176775
_question 0.0392864 0.0437548 *0.5184973 0.1164929 0.1084969 0.0684116 0.0039675 0.0392853 0.0191552 0.0295594 0.0130925
_is 0.1544213 0.0396650 0.0652480 *0.4423889 0.1376577 0.0845780 0.0231486 0.0116635 0.0045954 0.0123924 0.0242414
_whether 0.0423982 0.0160894 0.0478750 0.0692209 0.2712684 *0.4603364 0.0195624 0.0164463 0.0090764 0.0378646 0.0098622
_this 0.0177671 0.0046728 0.0064481 0.0014397 0.0007985 0.0131419 *0.4348802 0.1510058 0.0595676 0.1584601 0.1518182
_is 0.0186255 0.0007993 0.0280282 0.0042449 0.0015860 0.0030184 0.0187896 *0.4445156 0.2043135 0.1411511 0.1349381
_desirable 0.0266621 0.0009710 0.0089117 0.0018194 0.0019682 0.0052992 0.0390372 0.1594839 0.0912015 *0.5788434 0.0858026
_for 0.1361863 0.0033292 0.0071225 0.0019877 0.0039680 0.0235446 0.0400421 *0.2980067 0.1961447 0.1942762 0.0953919
_long 0.1032218 0.0012658 0.0046470 0.0009145 0.0023037 0.0198260 0.0663879 *0.5305993 0.1181806 0.1262876 0.0239058
_</s> *0.4627323 0.0022860 0.0092334 0.0013557 0.0017004 0.0085069 0.0082686 0.0134855 0.3631878 0.1029422 0.0263011
</s> *0.9761471 0.0021388 0.0025314 0.0011506 0.0019346 0.0038802 0.0025532 0.0030224 0.0017463 0.0031721 0.0017233
```

According to the matrices, the model seems to assign attention weights to the target words effectively, especially when the first column of the weight is discarded. This may be attributed to the nature of the basic dot-product attention mechanism, which is a fundamental attention mechanism where the similarity between the source and target token is determined by the dot

product of their vector representations.

To illustrate, in the first sentence above, the mechanism directs attention of "Frage" (the second column on the top) to "question" (with the * in the third column,) "Diese" (sixth column on the top row) focusing on "this" (seventh column,) "lange" (the seventh token) attending to "long" (highest weight in the eight column,) and "wünsch" to "desirable." However, as mentioned in the [Extra] section that the models were not sufficiently trained on a diverse and complex dataset, it fails to capture one crucial word: "Wartez," which should ideally be associated with "wait." Similar observations can be identified in the other four sample sentences.

[2023-11-30 00:29:01,321 INFO]		Die	Hoffnu	darauf	ist	nicht	unbere
The	0.1251628	0.1291053	*0.3880287	0.1602419	0.0619688	0.0911930	0.0442996
_hope	0.0424862	0.0305600	*0.7877944	0.0604341	0.0200232	0.0243714	0.0343307
_is	0.2631739	0.0348038	0.0487770	*0.3443772	0.2028192	0.0692179	0.0368311
_not	0.1274047	0.0271079	0.1126490	0.0791590	0.0426613	*0.4707426	0.1402754
.	0.1215210	0.0137890	0.1145365	0.0443769	0.0209275	0.0455809	*0.6392682
</s>	*0.9528099	0.0079576	0.0161316	0.0072057	0.0049329	0.0044875	0.0064746

[2023-11-30 00:28:59,465 INFO]		Durch	die	Strukt	assung	konnte	die	Effekt	im	Untern	ssektor	_verbes	_werden
The	0.0303132	0.0877404	0.0612229	0.0535184	*0.3317474	0.0282061	0.0196782	0.2534123	0.0057940	0.0264175	0.0144321	0.0629731	0.0245443
_solution	0.0076996	0.0109565	0.0132700	0.0517278	*0.4795091	0.0204527	0.0054798	0.2308866	0.0050408	0.0942561	0.0330577	0.0385795	0.0909738
_was	0.109252	0.049251	0.021571	0.0126174	0.0315193	0.2407232	0.0201269	0.0454767	0.0695959	0.0097976	0.0095275	0.1284365	0.0942145
_to	0.0416823	0.0314859	0.0076160	0.0086703	0.0505318	*0.2760197	0.0400067	0.1371876	0.0089488	0.0180678	0.0033428	0.2780062	0.1135421
_improve	0.0085574	0.0050682	0.0014694	0.0022374	0.0599250	0.0183121	0.0393406	0.2014181	0.0106756	0.0113858	0.0132000	*0.4817946	0.1466158
_efficiency	0.0218698	0.0020961	0.0020392	0.0015551	0.0082567	0.0063444	0.0792300	*0.6094489	0.0324196	0.1071153	0.0653725	0.0443525	0.0198950
_in	0.1533988	0.0274558	0.0085845	0.0011240	0.0025618	0.0212382	0.0534495	0.0609124	*0.4974338	0.0604724	0.0692143	0.0245269	0.0196356
The	0.1245498	0.0021861	0.0015263	0.0008221	0.0065326	0.0044562	0.0105514	0.0754298	0.1380412	*0.3373036	0.2654656	0.0296960	0.0121664
_business	0.0315117	0.0005971	0.0001853	0.0006944	0.0046613	0.0022742	0.0011492	0.0511579	0.0242541	*0.5607882	0.3098911	0.0094619	0.0033735
_sector	0.1082845	0.0020179	0.0003904	0.0007459	0.0056640	0.0033662	0.0013185	0.0321048	0.0221877	0.0683937	*0.7386395	0.0107041	0.0061830
.	*0.6650869	0.0503031	0.0129594	0.0063905	0.0104654	0.0294050	0.0261232	0.0549604	0.0164363	0.0076389	0.0133120	0.0554444	0.0433943
</s>	*0.9682005	0.0050113	0.0010606	0.0010032	0.0043045	0.0011022	0.0008462	0.0048856	0.0019895	0.0030259	0.0014131	0.0040709	0.0023275

[2023-11-30 00:29:01,471 INFO]		Nunmehr	forder	unsere	Mitbrue	konkre	und	wirkssa	Maßnah
Our	0.0295472	0.3159505	0.0321347	*0.3920898	0.1575542	0.0522084	0.0036921	0.0063271	0.0104959
_fellow	0.0063149	0.0117762	0.0129427	0.0119256	*0.9347728	0.0092317	0.0018986	0.0026891	0.0084485
_citizens	0.0091238	0.0071551	0.0183239	0.0161579	*0.8567145	0.0038587	0.0036046	0.0015047	0.0035570
_are	0.0534859	*0.4318375	0.3826968	0.0268026	0.0258183	0.0378652	0.0070653	0.0053835	0.0290450
_now	0.0297086	*0.4563484	0.4021174	0.0068224	0.0181273	0.0306335	0.0023553	0.0073532	0.0465338
_calling	0.0401695	*0.0670290	*0.7546269	0.0070469	0.0285240	0.0299286	0.0026041	0.0071432	0.0629278
_for	*0.3896150	0.0793245	0.2000899	0.0541317	0.0217267	0.1253263	0.0270115	0.0320153	0.0707592
_concrete	0.0083397	0.0034355	0.0075184	0.0142826	0.0148305	*0.5818925	0.0672025	0.1057536	0.1967447
_and	0.0182056	0.0014923	0.0087954	0.0027471	0.0102082	0.0212436	*0.6031264	0.0555602	0.2786210
_effective	0.0278689	0.0015297	0.0058739	0.0029251	0.0058679	0.0174296	0.0197955	*0.8433740	0.0753355
_measures	0.0731467	0.0032478	0.0175277	0.0058547	0.0297234	0.0117037	0.0124714	0.0566390	*0.7896856
.	*0.6108956	0.1539078	0.0300089	0.0386785	0.0169837	0.0143593	0.0061817	0.0284824	0.1005022
</s>	*0.9689732	0.0051289	0.0043655	0.0104054	0.0069057	0.0019392	0.0001467	0.0013843	0.0007512

[2023-11-30 00:28:57,696 INFO]		Der	Inhalt	des	Vorsch	ist	-	wenn	man	es	_jurist	_betrac	-		
The	0.0737022	0.1027455	0.1583431	0.0537048	0.0634222	0.0653405	0.0982435	*0.1622973	0.0257888	0.0162057	0.0417868	0.0179192	0.0266458	0.0051977	0.0083998
_content	0.0074431	0.0167688	*0.5895981	0.0173137	0.2522738	0.0107283	0.0132477	0.0067483	0.0012618	0.0010667	0.0183474	0.0160846	0.0086925	0.0021346	0.0419307
_of	0.1461915	0.0275396	*0.1076179	*0.2654389	0.0412045	0.1279826	0.0684875	0.0160070	0.0074377	0.0139772	0.0318362	0.0212138	0.0351570	0.0286580	0.0514104
The	0.0879644	0.0113135	0.0295066	*0.4929721	0.2573861	0.0276555	0.0182032	0.0046827	0.0045845	0.0089618	0.0105657	0.0248798	0.0120459	0.0037091	0.0063691
_proposal	0.0280348	0.0024619	0.0436093	0.0409158	*0.8302416	0.0116447	0.0068540	0.0018224	0.0010612	0.0009309	0.0044551	0.0141255	0.0055043	0.0032291	0.0051094
_is	0.0180236	0.0073993	0.0207773	0.0106123	0.0097128	*0.3684602	0.1787343	0.0321425	0.0078422	0.0114972	0.0465416	0.0155034	0.0412704	0.0244174	0.2070656
_limited	0.0065326	0.0095483	0.0364441	0.0046991	0.0051852	0.0471883	0.1931746	0.0184235	0.0038275	0.0052056	0.0293784	0.0191217	0.0357125	0.0044870	*0.5810714
-	0.0473005	0.0165886	0.0176540	0.0079307	0.0051433	0.0333511	*0.5471674	0.1147214	0.0095483	0.0186132	0.0080882	0.0385578	0.0098676	0.0187325	0.0339354
_if	0.0080150	0.0022528	0.0056010	0.0015655	0.0024627	0.0047453	0.0187820	*0.3892056	0.0657959	0.0428354	0.1556859	0.1235362	0.1351668	0.0099454	0.0343143
_lit	0.0221620	0.007327	0.0033291	0.0011770	0.0018397	0.0013925	0.0042155	0.0194304	0.1246263	0.1036627	0.1793979	0.1779907	*0.3315624	0.0099262	0.0269550
_is	0.0506004	0.0008440	0.0053057	0.0008176	0.0025537	0.0051254	0.0039938	0.0052012	0.0624311	0.0722782	0.2257553	0.0764127	*0.3892248	0.0378193	0.0619170
_purely	0.0109357	0.0002808	0.0021551	0.0002384	0.0005212	0.0003295	0.0023527	0.0023175	0.0163696	0.0361460	0.2500034	0.1810707	*0.4311605	0.0176071	0.0485120
_legal	0.0044925	0.0000921	0.0004990	0.0001958	0.0001781	0.0000084	0.0005055	0.0004676	0.0024233	0.0041843	0.0109600	*0.6134307	0.3122334	0.0331409	0.0171084
.	*0.3169578	0.0019655	0.0109875	0.0012553	0.0028090	0.0017048	0.0107929	0.0136892	0.0077664	0.0148215	0.0532848	0.1021072	0.2376737	0.2113941	0.0127902
</s>	*0.9388282	0.0017939	0.0039064	0.0008859	0.0023324	0.0016072	0.0037331	0.0052669	0.0041287	0.0018516	0.0137072	0.0106840	0.0081728	0.0010881	0.0020137

In this assignment, I worked on training and evaluating NMT models with attention for the German-English language pair using the Europarl corpus. The preprocessing steps were thorough, resulting in well-organized datasets. Three types of models—RNN without attention, RNN with attention, and Transformer—were trained and evaluated.

Overall, there was a progressive improvement in BLEU and chrF2 scores as models transitioned from RNN without attention to RNN with attention and Transformer. However, a notable performance gap between the test and validation sets indicated potential issues in training diversity.

Individual translation analyses and attention matrices revealed occasional inaccuracies in attention weight assignments, emphasizing the need for more diverse training data. The assignment provided valuable insights into attention mechanisms, the importance of diverse datasets, and nuances in NMT

model evaluation.

Assignment 5: Beam Search and Multilingual Models

Exercise 1: Beam search

After completing the previous assignment, I aimed to assess the impact of various beam sizes on translation quality. For this analysis, I selected the transformer model at step 50000 due to its superior performance. I systematically varied the beam size using the "-beam_size" parameter in the "onmt_translate" command, setting it to 1, 5, 10, 15, and 20 individually. Following the translation and decoding of .bpe files, I computed BLEU and chrF2 scores. The resulting scores for translations with different beam sizes are outlined below.

Beam Size	BLEU Score	chrF2 Score
1	31.9	56.7
5	32.4	56.8
10	32.0	56.5
15	31.7	56.2
20	31.5	55.9

Outputs of BLEU and chrF2 scores of the translations with the beam sizes of 1, 5, 10, 15, and 20 can be found at https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uvHcbU8uxLQ4KODGE1nw_gq59d1oJTNRzkiG6QE2IRw/edit?usp=sharing.

To further investigate the impact of beam size in detail, I sampled a long and complex sentence from the translation outputs. While transformer models are generally effective in handling such sentences, variations arise based on different beam sizes. The variations in translation are provided below.

Source:

Ferner ist es von entscheidender Bedeutung, dass wir heute langfristige Strategien entwickeln, dass wir in der Lage sind, gemeinsam Planungsüberlegungen anzustellen, dass wir auf beiden Seiten wissen, was in zehn, zwanzig Jahren unsere gemeinsamen Interessen sind, damit wir unsere praktische Politik darauf einstellen können.

Reference:

Furthermore, it is of decisive importance that we are today developing long-term strategies, that we are in a position to make joint plans and that both sides know what our common interests will be in 10 or 20 years' time, so that we can base our practical policy on them.

Beam size 1:

It is also crucial that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to make joint thinking, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years' time, so that we can adapt our practical policies to them.

Beam size 5:

It is also crucial that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to take joint thinking, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years' time, so that we can adapt our practical policies to them.

Beam size 10:

It is also crucial that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to take joint thinking, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years' time, so that we can adapt our practical policies to them.

Beam size 15:

It is also crucial that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to work together, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years, so that we can adapt our practical policies to them.

Beam size 20:

It is also crucial that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to work together, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years, so that we can adapt our practical policies to them.

In the two underlined sections of this sentence, an enhancement in the naturalness of language is observed. With the beam size set to 1, the first section is translated as "make joint thinking," sounding unnatural. At beam sizes 5 and 10, the phrase is rendered slightly differently as "make joint thinking," still maintaining an unnatural tone. Beam sizes 15 and 20 offer the most natural translation, expressing it as "work together." Although not a literal translation which may explain slightly lower scores, especially when compared character to character (chrF2), this adjustment manages to capture

the essence of the meaning, providing a more natural translation. The same pattern is observed in the second section. Initially, beam sizes 1, 5, and 10 produce an unnatural translation as "in ten or twenty years' time," while increasing the beam size to 15 and 20 results in the more natural rendition "in ten or twenty years."

In summary, higher beam sizes (15, 20) tend to produce more natural translations, capturing the essence of the source text. While lower beam sizes (1, 5, 10) may yield higher BLEU and chrF2 scores, they may introduce subtle unnaturalness in the translations.

Additional Parameter Adjustments

With additional adjustments of parameters (-beam_size 5 -n_best 5 -verbose,) the best 5 hypotheses of the beam search are outputted in the translation file, and the best sentence is shown in the .err file with the prediction score (the lower, the better). The 5 best sentences according to the beam search hypothesis are as follow.

1. It is also crucial that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to take joint thinking, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years' time, so that we can adapt our practical policies to them.
2. It is also crucial that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to make joint thinking, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years' time, so that we can adapt our practical policies to them.
3. It is also vital that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to make joint thinking, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years' time, so that we can adapt our practical policies to them.
4. It is also crucial that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to take joint thinking, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years' time, so that we can adapt our practical policies to this.
5. It is also crucial that we develop long-term strategies today, that we are able to make joint thinking, that we know on both sides what our common interests are in ten or twenty years' time, so that we can adapt our practical policies to this.

The best sentence selected is shown below. For this sentence, the model assign the prediction score of -21.4313 to the translation indicating a higher level of confidence in the quality of the generated translation.

```
[2023-12-02 00:49:34,824 INFO]
SENT 9: ['_Ferner', '_ist', '_es', '_von', '_entscheidender', '_Bedeutung', ',', '_dass', '_wir',
'_heute', '_langfristige', '_Strategien', '_entwickeln', ',', '_dass', '_wir', '_in', '_der', '_Lage',
'_sind', ',', '_gemeinsam', '_Planungsüber', '_legungen', '_anzustellen', ',', '_dass', '_wir',
'_auf', '_beiden', '_Seiten', '_wissen', ',', '_was', '_in', '_zehn', ',', '_zwanzig', '_Jahren',
'_unsere', '_gemeinsamen', '_Interessen', '_sind', ',', '_damit', '_wir', '_unsere', '_praktische',
'_Politik', '_darauf', '_einstellen', '_können', '.']
PRED 9: _It _is _also _crucial _that _we _develop _long - term _strategies _today , _that _we _are
_able _to _take _joint _thinking , _that _we _know _on _both _sides _what _our _common _interests _are
_in _ten _or _twenty _years ' _time , _so _that _we _can _adapt _our _practical _policies _to _them .
PRED SCORE: -21.4313
```

Exercise 2: Multilingual NMT

In this exercise, I used a many-to-one (German, French, and Czech to English) translation model given a promising improvement compared to a single pair model shown in class. However, I am concerned that the distinctive linguistic features of the three source languages—German, French, and Czech—coupled with the limited learning dataset, might yield less impressive results, which could potentially impact the effectiveness of zero-shot translation. This might result in challenges in achieving high-quality translations when the model encounters languages it hasn't explicitly been trained on.

During the encoding model training with spm_train, I adjusted vocab size to 3000 to handle a larger dataset containing three languages.

Then, I applied the encoding model to encode the train, test, and val files of all four languages. This produces 12 files below.

```
test.bpe.cs test.bpe.en train.bpe.cs train.bpe.en val.bpe.cs val.bpe.en  
test.bpe.de test.bpe.fr train.bpe.de train.bpe.fr val.bpe.de val.bpe.fr
```

Then, I added the prefix tag <2en> to the source language train files (train.bpe.fr, train.bpe.de, and train.bpe.cs.) resulting in three tagged files:

```
train.bpe.de-en.de train.bpe.fr-en.fr train.bpe.cs-en.cs.
```

For the autoencoding task, I added the prefix tag of their own languages, <2de> <2fr> and <2cs>, to the related train files (train.bpe.de, train.bpe.fr, and train.bpe.cs, respectively.) This results in three additional files:

```
train.bpe.de-de.de train.bpe.fr-fr.fr train.bpe.cs-cs.cs
```

After that, I appended these six tagged files to create a train.source file in the following order:

```
train.bpe.de-en.de train.bpe.fr-en.fr train.bpe.cs-en.cs  
train.bpe.de-de.de train.bpe.fr-fr.fr train.bpe.cs-cs.cs.
```

I created a train.target file with `train.bpe.en`. I repeated the same steps to create test.source, test.target, val.source, and val.target. I trained a translation model using `onmt_train`.

Next, I generated vocabulary files with frequency information using the `onmt_build_vocab` command. In the `config_vocab.yaml` file, I set the number of samples for vocabulary construction to 1,000,000 to mitigate occurrences of <unk>. Subsequently, I proceeded to train the model using the `onmt_train` command. Upon applying the multilingual many-to-one model for translating source languages (German, French, and Czech) to English, I computed both BLEU and chrF2 scores. The obtained scores are presented below.

Translation Pair	BLEU	chrF2
German to English (Model Step 30,000)	40.2	60.3
German to English (Model Step 40,000)	39.1	59.5
German to English (Model Step 50,000)	39.1	59.3
French to English (Model Step 30,000)	0.1	12.0
French to English (Model Step 40,000)	0.1	12.5
French to English (Model Step 50,000)	0.1	12.4
Czech to English (Model Step 30,000)	0.1	11.8
Czech to English (Model Step 40,000)	0.1	12.5
Czech to English (Model Step 50,000)	0.1	12.1

Score outputs can be found at

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1oqb268jNiD4TAI4KaXLDEXFydIkuv0T_wfgowg1PbhM/edit?usp=sharing.

As indicated by the score table, the BLEU and chrF2 scores for the French and Czech languages are significantly low. This can be attributed to the fact that French and Czech belong to different language families — French to the Romance language family and Czech to the Slavic language family. Multilingual models are challenged to grasp shared linguistic features among source languages to ensure accurate translation. In contrast, German exhibits relatively higher scores, benefiting from its

membership in the same language family as the target language, English, so there are more shared linguistic characteristics.

Zero-shot translation

To assess the model's capability to translate from source languages unseen during training to English, I performed zero-shot translation by applying the model to language pairs not encountered during training: de->fr, de->cs, and fr->cs. The model should learn to generalize its translation capabilities across multiple source languages to the target language without having direct examples of translations between those source languages.

In this context, I observed a limitation in the performance of the many-to-one model, specifically trained on German, French, and Czech to English, when tasked with zero-shot translation. For instance, when attempting to translate from German to French and specifying <2fr> in the German test file, the model generated English translations instead of French, and vice-versa. The examples are shown below.

test.bpe.de-fr.de

```
<2fr> _Ein _Mann _mit _einem _orange farbene n _Hut , _der _etwas _an st ar r t .  
<2fr> _Ein _Bo st on _T er ri er _läu f t _ü ber _sa f ti g - gr ün es _Gras _vor _einem _wei ßen _Z a un  
.  
<2fr> _Ein _Mä dchen _in _einem _K ar ate an zug _bri cht _ein _B re t t _mit _einem _T r itt .  
<2fr> _F ün f _Leute _in _W inter j ack en _und _mit _H el men _stehen _im _Schnee _mit _Schne em ob  
il en _im _Hintergrund .  
<2fr> _Leute _Re par ieren _das _D ach _eines _H aus es .  
<2fr> _Ein _hell _gekleide ter _Mann _fotograf iert _eine _Gruppe _von _Mä nner n _in _dun kl en _An z  
ü gen _und _mit _Hü ten , _die _um _eine _Frau _in _einem _tr ä ger lo sen _Kleid _herum _stehen .  
<2fr> _Eine _Gruppe _von _Menschen _steht _vor _einem _I g lu .
```

test.de-fr_multi_en_30000

```
A man in an orange hat hugging at something.  
A Boston terrier runs across the grass in front of a white fence.  
A girl in a karate uniform breaks a board with a kick.  
Five people in winter jackets and helmets are standing in the snow with a snow-covered background.  
People repairing the roof of a house.  
There is a man photographs of men wearing dark suits and hats, and a woman in a light colored dress  
are standing around a woman.  
A group of people are standing in front of an igloo.
```

test.bpe.fr-de.fr

```
<2de> _Un _homme _avec _un _chapeau _orange _regardant _quelque _chose .  
<2de> _Un _ter ri er _de _Bo st on _court _sur _l ' herbe _ver do y ante _devant _une _cl ô ture  
_blanche .  
<2de> _Une _fille _en _tenue _de _kar at é _br isant _un _bâ t on _avec _un _cou p _de _p ied .  
<2de> _C in q _personnes _avec _des _vest es _d ' h i ver _et _des _cas ques _sont _debout _dans _la  
_neige , _avec _des _m ot on ei ges _en _arri è re - plan .  
<2de> _Des _gens _ré par ent _le _to it _d ' une _ma ison .  
<2de> _Un _homme _en _tenue _c la ire _photogra ph ie _un _groupe _d ' hom mes _portant _des _costu  
mes _som b res _et _des _chapeau x , _debout _autour _d ' une _femme _vê tue _d ' une _robe _bu st ier  
.
```

test.fr-de_multi_en_30000

```
Beautiful orange rode  
Blue Worker display of number 1 news.  
Nurses business controlling it out Names.  
Camp leading up process.  
Persons are emergency workers to get loose.  
Dressed Santa Caucasian, including a framed egg-shaped vocalist walks by.  
Dressed on a weigh.  
Dressed balance Fa's time out decorations, consolescent), tagged in a yard.
```

The primary training objective for this many-to-one model is to translate sentences from German, French, and Czech to English. Consequently, the model may become proficient at mapping input sentences in these source languages to their corresponding English translations. Moreover, the subword vocabulary employed for tokenization (vocab.multi_en.src) is shared among all source languages as shown below. This shared vocabulary approach may lead the model to overlook

language-specific patterns, potentially resulting in a bias towards English output even when provided with a language tag for a different language. This observation highlights the challenge of achieving effective zero-shot translation which requires specialized model architectures and training strategies.

_mit	18388	_Hund	3371	ine	2604
u	18267	_groupe	3354	_hraje	2590
_se	18001	_garçon	3350	_Hemd	2588
_auf	17926	_noir	3334	_zatimco	2588
_und	17855	_at	3329	ap	2572
es	17310	ung	3295	_o	2572
é	16952	_chien	3288	_žena	2572
_Muž	10736	me	3285	_am	2564
_à	10594	shirt	3282	_people	2548
_assis	3379	_wearing	2618	_train	2494

In summary, this assignment explored the impact of beam search on translation quality, revealing that higher beam sizes (15, 20) tended to produce more natural translations despite slightly lower BLEU and chrF2 scores. The challenges of training a multilingual many-to-one model were discussed, emphasizing the model's proficiency in translating within the same language family. However, the limitations of zero-shot translation were evident when translating between languages not explicitly trained on, underscoring the need for specialized approaches in such scenarios. Overall, the assignment provided valuable insights into the complexities of beam search and multilingual model training.

Assignment 6: Domain Adaptation

Exercise 1: Domain adaptation with fine-tuning

1. From a quick look, the texts in Europarl and Multi30k test sets are from different domains and contexts. The Europarl corpus contains the texts that are speeches or discussions related to European politics and policies while Multi30k corpus features image captions describing scenes or activities. Language use in Europarl is formal and political in contrast to a more casual and descriptive language found in Multi30k. The context of language in Europarl corpus revolves around European policies, state aid, peace negotiations, and resource requirements. On the other hand, Multi30k datasets are geared towards visual scenarios like a dog jumping over water or a woman pouring drinks.

Europarl

1. That is the job of the European Strategy for Employment and the Social Fund, which have huge sums of money and exceptionally large resources at their disposal, especially for countries like Greece.
2. On the other hand, districts which have not been affected by the storms will also suffer, as the National Forestry Office has decided to freeze cuts in forestation for four years.
3. First of all the report reveals Parliament' s single-minded determination to reduce state aid to ensure that the internal market functions flawlessly.
4. Mr President, it is pleasing that, despite certain delays and problems, the peace negotiations are going on both between Israel and Palestine and between Israel and Syria.
5. I conclude by referring to paragraph 15 of the resolution before the House relating to the resource requirements of our policies for change.
6. Considering that it is only today that we are dealing with a Commission proposal first made on 19 March 1998, even though Parliament responded relatively quickly, this time lag is a little too long.
7. The vote will take place tomorrow at 12 p.m.
8. Mr President, firstly I would like to extend my heartfelt congratulations to my colleague, Mr van Hulst.
9. Inspections by the maritime authorities and supervision within European ports must also be tightened up.
10. We are also doing a number of other things: in the European Union-China human rights dialogue, we have focused on a number of practical steps, including sending experts on assignment to Tibet, planning development assistance programmes and activities focusing on health, education and training for Tibetans.

Multi30k

1. Two male curling players are on ice sweeping the path in front of polished rock, a small crowd watches.
2. A gray and white dog jumping over standing water in the sand.
3. A blond-haired woman is pouring drinks at a bar.
4. An individual wearing rose jacket sits idle on a wooden bench.
5. A middle-aged man with red-hair and glasses holding an infant.
6. A small African child carries a younger child on his back.
7. Two people are laying down and kissing on a grassy lawn.
8. Music being played by several individuals while a happy crowd sits and listens.
9. A woman looks on as a man with folded arms is talking.
10. Professional baseball players during the All Star game watch an opponent at bat.

2. After segmenting test.fr in Europarl and Multi30k folders using sp_model trained from the Europarl dataset, I did not notice any differences in the segmented tokens between the two corpora. Because the model used in the segmentation process was trained on the Europarl dataset, which contains longer and more complex sentences, the segmenting model performed effectively on the Multi30k data, which has shorter and less complex sentences. The segmented units look accurate and complete. The differences in the final translation quality between the two datasets would probably stem from the lexical factor. As mentioned in the previous step, the texts in the two datasets belong to different contexts and domains.

Segmented Europarl

1. _Monsieur_le_Président , _je_suis_sûre_que_la_Commission_sera_soulagée_d'entendre_que_la_décharge_pour_l'exercice_1997_n'aura_visiblement_pas_les_mêmes_répercussions_que_la_décharge_1996_qui , _comme_vous_le_savez_tous , _a_débouché_sur_la_démission_forcée_de_la_Commission_Santer .
2. _Cette_absence_d'infrastructures_constitue_également_un_obstacle_à_l'implantation_d'entreprises_et_à_la_création_d'emplois .
3. _S'y_ajoutent_des_différences_entre_les_dispositions_juridiques_nationales_et_des_demandes_d'entraide_juridique_qui_traînent_en_longueur_ou_sont_laissées_sans_réponse .
4. _Monsieur_le_Président , _si_la_Commission_Santer_a_échoué , _c'est_aussi_parcé_que_elle_a_subi_un_échec_cuisant_sur_le_plan_du_contrôle_financier .
5. _Dans_l'urgence , _face_à_l'épreuve , _un_magnifique_élan_de_solidarité_s'est_manifesté : _solidarité_locale , _solidarité_nationale , _solidarité_inter_gouvernementale .

Segmented Multi30k

1. _Deux_hommes_créent_des_objets_dans_un_atelier_avec_des_outils .
2. _Une_équipe_de_pom-pom_girls_faisant_une_chorégraphie_sur_des_chaises .
3. _Une_petite_fille_regarde_dans_un_télescope_à_la_plage .
4. _Des_gens_regardent_tandis_que_les_participants_d'un_marathon_passent .
5. _Un_homme_dans_e_avec_un_chien_entre_ses_jambes .

3. After translating and decoding the .bpe files, I calculated BLEU and chrF2 scores. The results are in the table below.

	BLEU	chrF2
Europarl	33.4	59.4
Multi30k	22.2	44.6

Based on a lower BLEU and chrF2 scores of Multi30k translations, it is evident that the model trained with Europarl dataset seemed to struggle to provide a correct translation for Multi30k text. The first 15 translations of the Multi30k datasets are as follow:

Reference

1. A man in an orange hat starring at something.
2. A Boston Terrier is running on lush green grass in front of a white fence.
3. A girl in karate uniform breaking a stick with a front kick.
4. Five people wearing winter jackets and helmets stand in the snow, with snowmobiles in the background.
5. People are fixing the roof of a house.
6. A man in light colored clothing photographs a group of men wearing dark suits and hats standing around a woman dressed in a strapless gown.
7. A group of people standing in front of an igloo.
8. A boy in a red uniform is attempting to avoid getting out at home plate, while the catcher in the blue uniform is attempting to catch him.
9. A guy works on a building.
10. A man in a vest is sitting in a chair and holding magazines.
11. A mother and her young son enjoying a beautiful day outside.
12. Men playing volleyball, with one player missing the ball but hands still in the air.
13. A woman holding a bowl of food in a kitchen.
14. Man sitting using tool at a table in his home.
15. Three people sit in a cave.

Source

1. Un homme avec un chapeau orange regardant quelque chose.
2. Un terrier de Boston court sur l'herbe verdoyante devant une clôture blanche.
3. Une fille en tenue de karaté brisant un bâton avec un coup de pied.
4. Cinq personnes avec des vestes d'hiver et des casques sont debout dans la neige, avec des motoneiges en arrière-plan.
5. Des gens réparent le toit d'une maison.
6. Un homme en tenue claire photographie un groupe d'hommes portant des costumes sombres et des chapeaux, debout autour d'une femme vêtue d'une robe bustier.
7. Un groupe de personnes debout devant un igloo.
8. Un garçon en uniforme rouge essaie d'éviter de sortir du marbre, tandis que le receveur en tenue bleue essaie de l'attraper.
9. Un gars travaille sur un bâtiment.
10. Un homme en gilet est assis dans une chaise et tient des magazines.
11. Une mère et son jeune fils profitant d'une belle journée dehors.
12. Des hommes jouant au volleyball, avec un joueur ratant le ballon mais avec les mains toujours en l'air.
13. Une femme tenant un plat de nourriture dans une cuisine.
14. Un homme assis à une table chez lui, en train d'utiliser un outil.

15. Trois personnes sont assises dans une grotte.

Target

1. A man with an orange hat watching something.
2. A berth of Boston is on the verdant herbs in front of a white fence.
3. A girl in the possession of heroin breaking a stick with a coup.
4. Five people with winter gestures and castles are dumb in the snow, with the back-sumps.
5. People are repairing the roof of a house.
6. A man who has a clear photograph of a group of men with sombre suits and herds, rallying around a woman in a warlord of a robby.
7. There is a group of people who are at risk in the face of a gigo.
8. A single boy is trying to avoid getting out of the marble, while the blue recipient is trying to catch it.
9. A boys work on a building.
10. A gilet man is sitting in a chair and keeping magazines.
11. A mother and her young son taking advantage of a beautiful day outside.
12. People playing football, with a player buying the ball but with the hands of the air.
13. A woman with a food plate in a kitchen.
14. A man sitting at a table at home is using a tool.
15. Three people are sitting in a farce.

The translations contain inaccuracies in word choice, grammatical errors, issues with phrasing and fluency, misinterpretation, and inconsistencies. For example, in sentence 11, the verb “profitant de” is translated as “taking advantage of,” instead of “enjoying.” A difference in domains of the two corpora shows a clear effect on the translation in sentence 6 and 8, which are more about the descriptions of a situation.

Sentence 6

- **Source**
Un homme en tenue claire photographie un groupe d'hommes portant des costumes sombres et des chapeaux, debout autour d'une femme vêtue d'une robe bustier.
- **Reference**
A man in light colored clothing photographs a group of men wearing dark suits and hats standing around a woman dressed in a strapless gown.
- **Translation**
A man who has a clear photograph of a group of men with sombre suits and herds, rallying around a woman in a warlord of a robbly.

Sentence 8

- **Source**
A boy in a red uniform is attempting to avoid getting out at home plate, while the catcher in the blue uniform is attempting to catch him.
- **Reference**
Un garçon en uniforme rouge essaie d'éviter de sortir du marbre, tandis que le receveur en tenue bleue essaie de l'attraper.
- **Translation**
A single boy is trying to avoid getting out of the marble, while the blue recipient is trying to catch it.

4. In the fine-tuning step, I specified the following parameters:

```
train_from: /scratch/project_2001403/natchsan/lab6/europarl_model/transformer_fr_en_step_50000.pt
train_steps to 60000
save_checkpoint_steps: 2000
keep_checkpoint: 5
valid_steps: 2000
```

The accuracy values in each step, starting at 92.54 at step 52000/60000 and reaching 99.78 at the last step (60000/60000), indicate that the model learns to predict the segments more accurately as the training steps progress, and it predicts all the segments correctly (100% accurately) upon the completion of the training process. This is not a surprising phenomenon since the vocab files are from the Europarl dataset, which contains a lot more vocabs. Subsequently, when trained and validated with the Multi30k data, the model performs very well. However, although the fine-tuning process seems to go well, this unusually high accuracy score may be a sign that the model becomes overfit to the Multi30k dataset.

Step	Accuracy (%)
52000	92.54
54000	98.19
56000	99.39
58000	99.68
60000	99.78

5. I used the fine-tuned models at steps 56000, 58000, and 60000 to translate the test sets of Europarl and Multi30k data. Then, I calculated BLEU and chrF2 scores of each model. The scores of the original model and the fine-tuned models are in the table below.

Model	BLEU (Europarl)	chrF2 (Europarl)	BLEU (Multi30k)	chrF2 (Multi30k)
Original 50000	33.4	59.4	22.2	44.6
Fine-tuned 56000	10.9	31.8	54.2	70.8
Fine-tuned 58000	9.2	29.7	54.0	70.6
Fine-tuned 60000	8.4	28.7	54.3	70.5

The fine-tuning of models, compared to their original settings, results in a notable discrepancy in translation quality between the Multi30k and Europarl test sets. While demonstrating improved performance on the Multi30k test set, the fine-tuned models exhibit a substantial decline in translation quality on the Europarl test set.

The fine-tuning process involves incorporating vocabularies from the Europarl corpus and utilizing training and validation sets from the Multi30k corpus. This approach seems to bias the model towards the characteristics of the Multi30k dataset, leading to enhanced translation quality for that specific test set. However, this specialization comes at the cost of decreased performance on the Europarl test set, indicating a lack of balance in the fine-tuning process.

Despite the attempt at fine-tuning, the models show a skewed performance, favoring the Multi30k data over Europarl. The analysis of fine-tuning scores, particularly on the Europarl dataset, suggests that the optimal fine-tuned model is achieved at step 50000. This finding underscores the importance of selecting an appropriate fine-tuning step to achieve optimal performance on specific test sets. Adjustments to the fine-tuning process may be necessary to strike a better balance and enhance overall translation quality across diverse datasets.